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Contributors	All partners
Reviewed by	E.Cicognani & UNIBO team
E-mail Contact for queries	Gundula.Ludwig@uibk.ac.at
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Tab. 1 The SINCRONY Consortium

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Tab. 2 The SINCRONY Work Packages

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliberative Democracy, Youth and Intersectionality

This literature review acts as the conceptual and methodological backbone of the Intersectional Inclusion in Deliberation and Participation with Youth (SINCRONY) project, which aims to ensure the meaningful inclusion of youth who experience social disadvantage and marginalisation in deliberative and participatory processes. The drafting of the literature review was a collaborative process. The nine participating organizations of the SINCRONY project: Alma Mater Studiorum-Universita di Bologna, The University of Manchester, Universidade Do Porto, ALDA (Association Europeenne Pour Democratie Locale), Wedo Project (Intelligence Made Easy SL), Aalborg Universitet, Turun Yliopisto, Universite de Geneve, and Universitaet Innsbruck, conducted initial reviews of relevant qualitative and quantitative texts on intersectionality and youth participation. The participating organizations also conducted reviews of existing initiatives through which youth participation has been institutionalized within each country's context. These initial reviews highlighted existing theoretical and policy gaps in intersectional perspectives on deliberation and youth participation and provided a roadmap for the questions that are raised in this literature review. Further, by bringing in feminist and critical race perspectives, the literature review points to directions that the SINCRONY project can take to ensure the meaningful and robust participation of marginalized youth in deliberative processes.

1. Introduction

Paradoxically, a literature review on the entanglement of deliberative democracy, youth and intersectionality must focus on what has not yet been researched rather than what theoretical and empirical researched already exists. To date, few such contributions exist.

The research gaps are multiple, including theoretical gaps about theorizing deliberative democracy from an intersectional perspective as well empirical ones about practices of democracy. Thus, a systematic revision and re-writing of deliberative democracy theory from an intersectional perspective remains absent from debates in social sciences (Ackerly 2007; Palacios 2016). While intersectionality has long been a gender studies “buzzword” (Davis 2008) intersectionality has rarely appeared in debates and theorizations of deliberative democracy (Wojciechowska 2019, 896). This scholarly gap mirrors the ongoing white, androcentric, Eurocentric, heteronormative and ability-centred norms about political subjects, political agency and politics that largely continue to shape democratic theory despite several decades of ongoing critiques from feminist, Black, anti-racist, post- and decolonial and critical disability scholars. Furthermore, this gap also echoes a lack of intersectional perspectives in concrete policymaking processes that still shape European politics on an international, supranational, national and local level. In recent decades, social movements and struggles have important contributed to the introduction of anti-discrimination regulations at the supranational and national levels—for example, the Treaty of Amsterdam in 1997—in the last decades. However, the concrete analysis of institutionalized participation and policymaking from an intersectional lens remains rare in the political sciences (see for institutionalized approaches Squires 2009; Verloo 2006, 2013).

Second, asserting this lack of intersectional perspectives in deliberative democracy theory becomes more accurate upon expanding the notion of democracy and not restricting political agency to adults. Here, theoretical and empirical work that investigates the potentials and challenges of expanding democracy to youth is uncommon. Meanwhile, it is even rarer to find contributions stray from viewing children and adolescents as a homogenous group and instead as heterogeneous through their multiple positions within the racialized, classed, gendered, heterosexualized, and abled-bodied-centred structures of oppression, violence and exclusion.

In that regard, the literature review is structured as follows: The first chapter is dedicated to a brief introduction on intersectionality (2) where we discuss its history, the potential and challenges using it as a critical approach to analysing social injustice and modes of operationalizing intersectionality (2). The next chapter (3) discusses intersectionality and youth as well as intersectional perspectives on youth participation, which is followed by feminist and critical race theory reflections on deliberative democracy (4). The subsequent chapter (5) discusses literature on deliberative

democracy and youth, while the final section (6) presents an intersectional lens for deliberation and youth participation.

Our underlying premise is that an intersectional approach can potentially provide a more profound and richer understanding of democracy (Ackerly 2007; Wojciechowska 2019). Given that modern societies are *structured* through gendered, raced, classed, heteronormative, religious, and ability-centred structures of oppression, increasing citizen participation in existing political structures is insufficient alone because these structures themselves are a materialization of power structures, structural violence and structural exclusion. Thus, an intersectional perspective on deliberative democracy holds the potential and aim to make democracy (more) democratic by radically broadening the understanding of what it is as well as how both deliberants and deliberative processes and systems can become more diverse and thus more democratic (Zlotnik Raz/Almog 2023, 91; Wojciechowska 2019). Hence, an intersectional perspective on deliberative democracy moves towards radical democratic theory (Laclau/Mouffe 1985; Mouffe 1993) in this attempt to broaden the understanding of democracy. At the same time, we will show that intersectionality and deliberative democracy are undergoing tension: Intersectionality's commitment to social justice means it also serves as critical lens for challenging power structures that are inherent to deliberative democracy as a white, western, androcentric concept.

2. Defining an Intersectional Approach

At its outset, intersectionality can be described as an approach, an analytical tool, and a political project for understanding, analyzing and transforming multiple, complex dimensions of power and inequality. An intersectional framework highlights that the organization of power and people's experiences of it are not shaped by a single axis or category of social division but by multiple categories, including gender, sexuality, race, class, and disability. An intersectional perspective sees these categories as mutually constituted and reinforcing, intersecting in people's lived experiences of people such that their effects cannot be disaggregated. Finally, intersectionality is a political project that seeks to transform relationships of power to achieve social justice.

While useful, this starting definition of intersectionality paradoxically contradicts many of its surrounding questions and debates. The concept of intersectionality is considered one of feminist theory's most important contributions (McCall 2005), having been extended and applied across disciplinary, institutional, and even national boundaries. Despite its increased popularity, the concept remains marked by concerns around its vagueness and open-endedness (Davis 2008). What complicates the adoption and application of intersectionality within research and policy projects is the absence of a clear set of parameters and methodological guidelines on where and how it can be applied, with scholars arguing that intersectionality is methodologically agnostic

(Anthias 2013; Hancock 2013; Hopkins 2018; Oyewuwo/Walton 2023) and has no one specific method associated with it.

The multitude of ways that intersectionality has been employed in diverse contexts has helped it earn a reputation as a dynamic and “successful” (Davis 2008) approach, but has also led several scholars to both raise questions about the utility and limitations of intersectionality and express uncertainty about how it has been and should be employed as a method (Collins 2019; Cho/Crenshaw/McCall 2013; Davis 2008; Smooth 2013; Jordan-Zachery 2007; McCall 2005). Scholars like Smooth (2013), and May (2015) state that despite being widely cited and extensively applied, intersectionality is often invoked and applied in ways that misrecognize and flatten its critical potential. For instance, May (ibid.) states, “Practitioners can blunt its critical edge and transformative aims by moving away from a multilevel approach, delimiting it to the descriptive, or turning it into a version of pop-bead identity logics or single-axis notion of oppression” (ibid., 141). However, as Smooth (2013) argues, the debates around what constitutes an intersectional approach “should not detract from opportunities to address the very systems of inequality that intersectionality illuminates” (ibid., 31). In the spirit of identifying the transformative potentials of employing intersectionality, this section outlines some of its key conceptual and methodological tenets. A scholarly engagement with methodology is not concerned “solely with methods but with the philosophical underpinnings and the kinds of substantive knowledge that are produced in the application of methods” (McCall 2005, 1774).

This literature review does not intend to provide a static set of definitions and tools that can be applied in any straightforward way to research and political interventions, since intersectionality is not “a fixed method with set boundaries, hard-and-fast tenets, or predetermined subjects and schematics,” but instead “an interpretive orientation that leaves these factors as open questions to be taken up, to help expose how subjection and dominance operate, sometimes subtly” (May 2015, 4). Drawing on the work of intersectional theorists, the methodological tenets in the following sections “are not offered as guarantees or as some kind of fail-safe formula for practicing intersectionality,” but rather should be seen as “akin to brushstrokes in an in-process, many-layered portrait of intersectional orientations and politics” (ibid., 228). As Davis (2008) argues, although an intersectional lens may not provide “written-in-stone guidelines for doing feminist inquiry,” it “encourages complexity, stimulates creativity, and avoids premature closure, tantalizing feminist scholars to raise new questions and explore uncharted territory” (ibid., 79).

2.1 A Brief Intellectual History of Intersectionality

The first step in outlining the methodological tenets of intersectionality is tracing its intellectual and political genealogy. Smooth (2013) cautions against taking for granted “the historical roots of intersectionality and the politicized struggles associated with the term” (ibid., 16) and states that

as intersectionality travels across geographical and institutional contexts, “it is often stripped of the very elements that made it a critical theory with a social justice imperative” (ibid., 13). As scholars such as Bilge (2013), May (2015), and Smooth (2013) have argued, failing to locate the origins of intersectionality in the works of Black feminist¹ scholars and activists like Sojourner Truth, Anna Julia Cooper, Maria Stewart, Kimberlé Crenshaw, the Combahee River Collective, and Patricia Hill Collins, contributes to its “whitening” it being co-optation by neoliberal politics. Scholars like Collins and Bilge (2016), May (2015), Nash (2019) have highlighted that Black feminist activists and intellectuals have engaged with questions about the mutually constitutive nature of race, gender, class and sexuality since the nineteenth century.

May (2015) emphasises how in Anna Julia Cooper’s 1892 book “A Voice from the South by a Black Woman of the South” articulated the foundations of contemporary intersectional approaches: “Whether the context was religion, education, economics, literature, or history, Cooper refused to homogenize race or gender, or to treat any one factor as singular or primary” (ibid., 70). Cooper protested against the white supremacy and xenophobia that was present among white feminists and also reprimanded Black men for their adherence to sexism and patriarchy. Cooper wrote, “colored woman of to-day occupies...a unique position in this country...She is confronted by both a woman question and a race problem, and is as yet an unknown or an unacknowledged factor in both” (Cooper 1988, 134). May (2015) points out that Cooper’s intersectional framework extended to public debates around personhood, citizenship, civil rights and freedom.

Less than a century after Cooper expressed her ideas, the Combahee River Collective (2014) drew on their organizing experiences as Black feminists to provide a critical analysis of how the oppressive systems of racism, capitalism, patriarchy and homophobia intertwine. In their 1977 statement, they wrote, “The most general statement of our politics at the present time would be that we are actively committed to struggling against racial, sexual, heterosexual, and class oppression, and see as our particular task the development of integrated analysis and practice based upon the fact that the major systems of oppression are interlocking” (ibid., 271).

Most accounts of intersectionality ignore this larger history of Black feminist intellectual thought when they credit Kimberlé Crenshaw as having “coined” the term (Collins 2019, 121); however, as May (2015) argues, Crenshaw herself draws on this longer history of Black feminist theorizing and underscores that her work builds upon the ideas of nineteenth century Black feminists like Sojourner Truth and Anna Julia Cooper (1988, 68). Crenshaw’s work is nevertheless seen as having “catalyzed a tectonic shift in the nature of feminist theorizing by suggesting that black women’s experiences demanded new paradigms in feminist theorizing” (Cooper 2016, 386). In her essay titled, “Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of

¹ Borrowing from Jennifer Nash (2019), when referring to Black feminist theory, we refer to Blackness as a political category rather than as a marker of identity while remaining committed to foregrounding the intellectual, creative and political work of Black women (ibid., 5).

Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory and Antiracist Politics,” Crenshaw (1989) deployed the metaphor of intersectionality in response to a set of legal decisions that obscured and neglected Black women’s experiences of discrimination. Crenshaw (ibid.) elaborated the metaphor as follows:

Consider an analogy to traffic in an intersection, coming and going in all four directions. Discrimination, like traffic through an intersection, may flow in one direction, and it may flow in another. If an accident happens in an intersection, it can be caused by cars traveling from any number of directions and, sometimes, from all of them. Similarly, if a Black woman is harmed because she is in an intersection, her injury could result from sex discrimination or race discrimination...But it is not always easy to reconstruct an accident: Sometimes the skid marks and the injuries simply indicate that they occurred simultaneously, frustrating efforts to determine which driver caused the harm (ibid., 149).

Crenshaw used the intersection analogy to highlight the specific vulnerabilities faced by women who find themselves at the juncture of two or more power axes, but to also underline “antidiscrimination law’s continued inattention to black women, its failure to attend to the particular raced and gendered forms of violence black women endured, forms of invisibility that feminism and antiracism only replicated” (Nash 2019, 102).

By drawing on Black women’s experiences of oppression, Black feminist intellectuals and activists thus laid the ground for a sophisticated theorizing of power. In centering the experiences of Black women, Black feminist scholars and intellectuals reaffirmed their right to “speak and be heard as Black feminist knowers” (May 2015, 70). In doing so, they also challenged the epistemic injustice that Black women have historically faced. As Collins points out, this system of oppression “works to suppress the ideas of Black women intellectuals and to protect elite White male interests and worldviews” (2000, 5). Cooper also highlighted the epistemic violence that Black women face when she raised doubts about whether her voice would be allowed “an equal hearing at the bar of the nation” (1988, 202). Thus, in the work of Black feminist scholars and activists, intersectionality becomes an epistemological intervention that challenges dominant ways of thinking and resists practices that silence Black women.

By using the experiences of Black women to craft an analytical tool, intersectionality challenges Western social theory’s assumption that “experience is not a valued way of knowing” (Collins 2019, 12). However, this focus on Black women’s voices and experiences within the work of intersectional theorists has also led to criticism that intersectionality is “too particularistic,” or is, “too closely associated with the ideas and interests of women, Black people, poor people, and people in subordinated groups” (ibid.). Such criticism sees intersectionality as lacking wider

relevance or applicability. As May (2015) states, “The implication is that attending to Black womanhood entails some inherent narrowness: it is as if only some parts of intersectionality’s insights about simultaneous privilege and oppression and about the limits and distortions of ‘single-axis’ logics are perceived or taken up” (ibid., 25). May (ibid.) argues that such a reductive reading of intersectionality is itself based on the assumption that Black women themselves are a singular, undifferentiated, homogenous group (ibid., 26). Yuval-Davis echoes this when she writes, “I find it problematic . . . that the construction of ‘black woman’ is automatically assumed, unless otherwise specified, to be that of a minority black woman living in white Western societies. The majority of black women in today’s world are black women in black societies. This has major implications for a global intersectional stratification analysis” (Yuval-Davis 2007, 162).

2.2. Power structures and categories

While it is outside the scope of this review to highlight debates around the applicability of intersectionality in diverse contexts, it is critical to underline the relationship between identity and power that is invoked in these debates. Intersectionality is often dismissed as advocating an essentialist identity politics that valorizes the experiences of oppressed people, including women of colour and poor women. Engaging with the work of intersectionality theorists challenges such simplistic readings of both identity politics and intersectionality’s engagement with identity politics. As Collins argues, Black feminist intellectuals—including the Combahee River Collective—developed a robust framework of identity politics as part of which identity was seen as always under construction and, therefore, an important site of intellectual and activist engagement (Collins 2019, 138). However, over time, identity politics has come to be seen as an exclusionary and particularistic discourse that ‘reduces’ people to their identities (Collins 2019; Bohrer 2023). Collins (2019) argues that such misreadings of identity politics work to weaken the radical potential of the Black feminist theorizing. Crenshaw seems to anticipate a similar misreading of intersectionality when she underlines that it is not a “new, totalizing theory of identity” and is different from theorizations of identity politics that “frequently conflates or ignores intragroup difference (...) ignoring difference within groups contributes to tension among groups” (Crenshaw 1991, 1242). Despite the work by Crenshaw and other Black feminist scholars, intersectionality continues to be dismissed as a form of essentialist identity politics. Its engagement with gender, sexuality, race, class and other categories has invited criticism that the theory is more concerned with identity categories versus structures of inequality (Cho/Crenshaw/McCall 2013, 797). In responding to such criticism, intersectionality scholars have theorized on the relationships between identity, experience and structural power. For instance, Crenshaw (1991) further develops the concept of intersectionality into structural intersectionality, political intersectionality and representational intersectionality. *Structural intersectionality* reveals how a person’s social location is relevant to

and shapes their experiences. For example, it helps analyse how women of colour experience domestic violence and remedial reform differently from white women (ibid., 1245) or why a Black woman would not be considered for a job where the norm employee might be a white woman or a Black man (Verloo 2006, 213). *Political intersectionality* emphasizes how social locations—and specifically, a person’s location at the intersection of multiple identities—shapes their political agendas and political strategies. The concept raises questions about modes of political organizing, challenging universal and single-axis approaches to resistance (Verloo 2006; Cho/Crenshaw/McCall, 2013). Finally, *representational intersectionality* explains the relationship between representation and power, highlighting, for instance, the injurious impacts of racist humour.

In theorizing on structural intersectionality, political intersectionality, and representational intersectionality, Crenshaw (1991) directly engages with how identity should be conceptualized within an intersectional approach. She acknowledges that by rejecting essentialist notions of identity, intersectionality “owes a great deal to the postmodernist idea that categories we consider natural or merely representational are actually socially constructed in a linguistic economy of difference” (ibid., 1269). However, Crenshaw adds that postmodernist theory ignores the meaning of the social construction of categories and their political relevance by neglecting the significance or effects of these categories. Crenshaw’s discomfort with this rejection is further clarified by McCall’s (2005) work on the methodological implications of how categories are conceptualized within applications of intersectionality.

McCall (ibid.) suggests three ways to approaching categories within intersectional analysis: anti-categorical, inter-categorical, intra-categorical. Scholars who adopt the anti-categorical approach question the validity of analytical categories, arguing that a “wide range of different experiences, identities and social locations fail to fit neatly into any single ‘master’ category” (ibid., 1777). They see categories lacking a foundation in reality and view language as creating categories (rather than merely describing them). According to McCall (ibid.), research conducted using the anti-categorical approach has adopted methods such as genealogy, deconstruction and ethnography to challenge the singularity and separateness of a range of social categories.

The inter-categorical approach studies the nature of relationships among social groups and attempts to empirically chart the changing relationships among them. What distinguishes the inter-categorical approach from anti- and intra-categorical approaches is that relationships of inequality between different social groups are not just provided as the background or the context, but are the focus of the analysis itself. McCall (ibid.) states that adding any one category to the analysis complicates the inter-categorical approach, since it requires investigating the category’s multiple constituent groups.

The intra-categorical approach focuses on a “single social group at a neglected point of intersection of multiple master categories” and studies the diversity and differences of experiences *within* the group rather than across groups. It follows a longer tradition of social scientific research that focuses on in-depth studies on single groups, including research that employs ethnography and case study methods. McCall (ibid.) states that the intra-categorical approach is also reflected in the work of feminists of colour—and specifically Black feminist scholars—who advocate for a specific focus on the lives of Black women since their experiences were neither reflected in gender studies (which focused on white women) nor race studies (which focused on Black men). In doing so, feminists of colour also challenged political and scholarly works that treated women as a homogenous category.

According to McCall (ibid.), the intra-categorical approach is consistent with the intersectional framework adopted by feminists of colour by entailing a complete rejection of categorization or the social reality of categorization. As Anthias (2013) states, categories are necessary components of analysis meaning they cannot be completely abandoned (ibid., 13). An intersectional framework simultaneously maintains skepticism towards broad generalizations regarding any category, recognizing that analytical categories like gender, race, sexuality, class and ethnicity are socially constructed (Hancock 2013, 259) and that they do not determine the “complex texture of day-to-day life for individual members of the social group under study, no matter how detailed the level of disaggregation” (McCall 2005, 1782).

Recognizing categories as fluid and context-dependent does not preclude conceptualizing intersectionality as being ultimately concerned with understanding how categories reflect the workings of power (Crenshaw 1991; Chun/Lipsitz/Shin 2013; Misra/Curington/Green 2021). As Misra, Curington and Green (2021) state, “researchers can point to the fluidity and malleability of categories by deconstructing them; however, the act of deconstructing categories and pointing to their instability gives researchers greater traction at explaining how inequality works; it does not mean that inequality does not exist” (ibid., 14). Hence, recognising that categories such as race, class, gender and sexuality involve “boundary-making and hierarchy-making processes” is key to employing an intersectional framework since these categories have significant material effects (Anthias 2013, 7). An intersectional framework sees power as dynamic and shifting, and attempts to study the processes by which inequalities are produced, experienced and resisted (McCall 2005). Focusing on the workings of power allows intersectionality to draw attention to how privilege operates. By focusing on structures of gender, class, sexuality, race, ethnicity, ability, religion, nation, and gender identity, it highlights how, “although often treated as distinct aspects of an individual’s experiences, these privileged and marginalized identities interact simultaneously in complicated ways” (Case 2013, 6). As Collins (2019) states, this emphasis on the interaction between privilege and oppression is because categories like race, class and gender are often only

seen as relevant for subordinated people. Examining experiences of privilege, while complicated by the often-invisible ways in which privilege operates, “in order to raise awareness of unearned social group advantages, the conversation must stay tuned in to privilege itself as a concept and tangible benefits in the daily lives of dominant group members” (Case 2013, 2). Coston and Kimmel argue that intersectionality complicates a “dichotomous” and “universal” understanding of privilege. They employ an intersectional approach to study men’s experiences of masculinity, a privileged gender identity, and highlight how men with disabilities, gay men, and working-class men “see their gender privilege reduced and their masculinity questioned, not confirmed, through their other marginalized status” (Coston/Kimmel 2012, 109).

The above history of intersectionality challenges critiques that see intersectionality as perpetuating an essentialist (and therefore harmful) and reductive version of identity politics. Instead, it is a critical concept, a set of analytical and methodological tools, and an epistemological and political project that seeks to understand the dynamic and complex ways that power operates. Intersectionality studies the interactions between individuals and institutions, offering tools for analyzing how categories of race, class, gender, and sexuality are mutually constituted and enmeshed in these interactions. The following sections build on these salient tenets of intersectionality to further elaborate the methodological tools that the concept offers.

2.3 Methodological Tools of Intersectionality

2.3.1 Intersectionality is Attentive to Complexity

Understanding that power operates in complex ways is key to employing an intersectional framework. The framework’s complexity challenges the binary organization of the world that characterizes much of Western epistemology (Lorde 1984a; Misra/Curington/Green 2021). Rather than seeing categories like man/woman, white/Black as binaries, “reckoning with complexity instead means that intersectional researchers insist that these seemingly distinct and oppositional categories are linked, interactive and relational” (Misra/Curington/Green 2021, 12). Jordan-Zachery (2007) points to this complexity when she states that framing intersectionality as *interlocking* systems of oppression (Crenshaw 1991) does not mean that these interlocking systems can eventually be separated (Jordan-Zachery 2007, 260). Regarding her own identity as a Black woman, Jordan-Zachery states, “...my blackness cannot be separated from my womaness. In fact, I am not sure if I want them to separated. Sometimes my identity is like a ‘marble’ cake, in that my blackness is mixed intricately with my womaness and therefore cannot be separated or unlocked. In some of our analyses, we try to isolate and desegregate race and gender. How can we isolate and desegregate elements that are so intricately mixed?” (ibid., 261). Ken (2008) also provides a culinary metaphor, using sugar to describe how categories such as gender, race, and class are produced, how they interact, and the effects they produce. Using the

example of baking sugar cookies, Ken states that when someone adds sugar, eggs, and flour to the baker's bowl and beats them together, what remains in the bowl are not "a separate section of sugar, one of flour, and one of eggs, but a dough—a cohesive mass. By mixing all these ingredients together and baking them, she makes cookies; she uses the ingredients in a way that results in the construction of a different form of food" (ibid., 160). These different metaphors emphasize how identity categories must be seen as mutually constituted rather than separable systems of inequality (Ken/Helmuth 2021). An intersectional methodology must therefore resist simple, additive approaches that essentialize differences and do not recognize the complex ways that identities are constituted, represented and experienced. Misra, Curington and Green (2021) state that an additive approach assumes that people from certain groups will always experience greater privilege or oppression than those from other groups (ibid., 12).

Intersectionality also enables a more complex analysis of power by drawing attention to the multiple levels and arenas at which it operates. Anthias (2013) provides suggestions for arenas of investigation that intersectional frameworks can incorporate, namely organisational, representational, intersubjective, and experiential. These arenas are expanded upon as follows:

1. Organisational: How population categories are organised within institutional frameworks, e.g. family structures and networks, educational systems, political and legal systems, the state apparatus and the policing and surveillance system.
2. Representational (discourses): The images and texts, documents and information flows surrounding social divisions in different institutional frameworks.
3. Intersubjective (practices): Practices in relation to others, including non-person actors such as the police and the social security system. It also denotes patterns of practices concerning identity and otherness (such as practices of bonding, friendship and distancing).
4. Experiential (narratives): Narratives relating to meaning-making and sociality (including the affective, the emotional and the body). This includes narrations of identification, distinction and othering. (ibid., 11)

Similar to Crenshaw's theorization of structural, political, and representational intersectionality, Anthias's (2013) work on investigating multiple societal arenas highlights the abstract and ever-evolving nature of categories like race, class, gender and sexuality, while drawing attention to the social relations and inequalities that they produce.

The matter of complexity raises a question that scholars who employ an intersectional framework most grapple with: What is the appropriate level of detail that constitutes an intersectional lens? Intersectionality theorists do not offer a singular response, and the lack of a clear set of guidelines

concerning the level of detail again points to concerns around the methodological vagueness of intersectionality. However, several theorists state that this openness should be seen as an invitation to developing more complex inquiries. As Davis (2008) states,

“The infinite regress built into the concept – which categories to use and when to stop – makes it vague, yet also allows endless constellations of intersecting lines of difference to be explored. With each new intersection, new connections emerge and previously hidden exclusions come to light. The feminist scholar merely needs to ‘ask (an)other question’ and her research will take on a new and often surprising turn. She can begin to tease out the linkages between additional categories, explore the consequences for relations of power, and, of course, decide when another ‘question’ is needed or when it is time to stop and why”. (ibid., 77).

Misra, Curington and Green (2021) also recommend embracing the incompleteness of intersectional inquiries when they state, “No one project can cover every base; yet, they can be designed creatively to consider how simple additive categories may not fully uncover the social processes of interest. Intersectional researchers work to analyze the most salient statuses for their research question, recognizing that exploring other socially constructed dimensions of difference might lead to different insights” (ibid., 13–14). Their argument about the impossibility of any single research project being able to cover all dimensions of social processes highlights the partial and situated nature of knowledge produced by an intersectional lens. McCall (2005) likewise points to this, stating that intersectional frameworks may attempt to situate subjects within the full network of relationships that define their social locations, but “usually it is only possible to situate them from the partial perspective of the particular social group under study” (1781). Hence, the theory of intersectionality furthers the development of feminist standpoint theory (Yuval Davis 2012, 2017), which challenges “the god-trick of seeing everything from nowhere” (Haraway 1991, 189) and stresses the importance of accounting for the social positioning of both the researcher and the researched to highlight the partial and situated nature of the knowledge produced.

An intersectional methodology thus requires complex analyses of power, attention to how power operates at the interface between structures, institutions and individuals, and a reflexivity towards the situated nature of the knowledge produced. This complexity is further complemented by intersectionality’s emphasis on the contexts in which power operates.

2.3.2 Intersectionality is Attentive to Context

Challenging broad generalizations regarding any category requires seeing them as fluid and emergent by acknowledging the specific contexts in which they appear and operate (Anthias 2013,

8). An intersectional methodology draws attention to the spatial and temporal contexts in which power operates. As Misra, Curington and Green (2021) state that researchers who employ intersectional frameworks should think about “*when and where* a particular set of overlapping conditions matter the most” (ibid., 13). Fundamentally, the project’s specific context, including where it is being conducted, will shape which categories of analysis will be considered. As Smooth (2013) argues, “While race, gender, class, sexuality, and ability have been central to intersectionality approaches in the United States, these same categories may be less salient in other contexts where citizenship, language, and region may structure the formation of social hierarchies” (ibid., 12). Regarding context, researchers must also be attentive to how the experiences and meanings of race, gender, class and other statuses vary according to time, space, and place. Such attentiveness to context reveals “inseparability of both the structural and identity levels within intersectional analysis” and the continuous “construction and reconstruction of identity” (Abdellatif 2021, 59).

Abdellatif (2021) theorizes on her own “fragmented experience in two different contexts,” writing about her experiences of growing up in Egypt and then moving to the United Kingdom as an immigrant student. She (ibid.) states that while living in Egypt, where patriarchy is reinforced by religion, she had to regulate her life choices, including decisions on how to dress. Her move to the United Kingdom was marked by a greater awareness about her racial identity, which she had not been conscious of until then. Abdellatif states that a “monolith third-world discourse” shaped her experiences in the United Kingdom, as reflected in her unspoken everyday-life interactions as well as comments about her “exotic look” or accent. (ibid., 61). She also writes that the onset of the COVID-19 exacerbated her precarity because—unlike students from the United Kingdom—international students could not pause their studies, which would compromise their legal residency in the United Kingdom (ibid., 62). She wondered if establishing power and finding a sense of belonging in the United Kingdom over time would cause her racial identity to become less salient as a source of marginalisation. Abdellatif’s account highlights multiple, intersecting, and fluid dimensions of power where her awareness of her own gender, religious, and racial identity shifts across space and time.

Besides revealing the variability of experiences of race, gender, sexuality, class, age, and disability across time and space, attentiveness to context also reveals how the very meanings of these categories are constructed within particular contexts. What kind of research methods can researchers adopt to remain attentive to the contexts in which power operates? Hopkins (2018) suggests employing research methods in an open, exploratory and flexible manner to allow participants to raise and discuss issues they find important. For example, during a research project on minority young people’s experiences of racism and misrecognition in Scotland, researchers worked with an interview schedule of questions that they employed flexibly to give the research

participants space to raise the social divisions that were most significant to them. Being flexible with employing research methods allows researchers to be attentive to how categorizations are not “equally positioned or salient at all times...and be sensitive to the relationships between social categories, rather than presuppose them” (Anthias 2013, 14).

2.3.3 Intersectionality is Oriented Towards Social Justice

Intersectionality scholars like Ahmed (2012), May (2015), Misra, Curington & Green (2021), Smooth (2013), Jordan-Zachery (2007) emphasize the importance of acknowledging that their work is rooted in a commitment to dismantling structures of oppression that confront Black women and in the liberation of Black women and their communities. This is central to recognizing intersectionality’s origins in the works of Black feminist scholars and activists such as Maria Stewart, the Combahee River Collective, Patricia Hill Collins, and Kimberle Crenshaw is. Additionally, authors like Collins and Bilge (2016), Oyewuwo and Walton (2023), and Jordan-Zachery (2007) have suggested that intersectionality should not only be employed to just frame and describe inequality, but to work towards identifying concrete solutions and interventions. For example, Misra, Curington and Green (2021) state that intersectional knowledge produced through empirical research can be mobilised towards the goal of social justice by shaping policy, promoting collective action and dismantling multiple, intersecting hierarchies.

An intersectional framework enables political organizing that departs from single-axis struggles or a sole orientation towards “lowest-common-denominator politics” (Bohrer 2023, 177). Audre Lorde (1984a) articulates this by stating, “As a Black lesbian feminist, I find I am constantly encouraged to pluck out some one aspect of myself and present this as the meaningful whole, eclipsing or denying the other parts of self. But this is a destructive and fragmenting way to live. My fullest concentration of energy is available to me only when I integrate all the parts of who I am, openly (...). Only then can I bring myself and my energies as a whole to the service of those struggles which I embrace as part of my living” (ibid., 80). Her refusal to fragment herself, like Jordan-Zachery’s (2007) refusal to see their blackness and womanness as separate, reveals a complex form of subjectivity that rejects additive models of identity that also has implications for how possibilities of social justice are conceived.

Likewise, recognizing the fluid, contextual, and provisional nature of identity categories does not preclude that communities and collectivities can coalesce around them (Bohrer 2023). These communities can “aid in self-understanding, share wisdom, engage in collective self-defense, mutual aid, politicization, consciousness raising, direct action, as well as the creation of spaces of art, vitality, and joy” (ibid., 175). Crenshaw (1991), Cho, Crenshaw and McCall (2013) and May (2015) have argued that rather than seeing identity as a starting point, we should conceptualize it as the basis of *coalition*. May (ibid.) states that intersectionality enables a politics of coalition where

“to contest shared logics across systems of domination, solidarities need to be forged via mutual commitments, not via principles of homogeneity or sameness” (ibid., 4). Focusing on coalitions that are forged to resist multiple modes of power highlights that “intersectionality is not a mere analytical framework or critical theory; it is centrally aimed at the transformation of the world” (Bohrer 2023, 177).

2.4 Institutionalizing Intersectionality?

Keeping social justice at the heart of intersectionality requires attentiveness to the contexts where it is invoked and applied. For example, when discussing the applications of intersectionality to policy projects May (2015) argues that in “the EU (European Union), there is a need for healthy skepticism about state engagements with intersectionality politics” (ibid., 153). May’s critique comes at a time when diverse governance institutions, including bodies like the United Nations and the European Union, are increasingly employing intersectionality as a policy tool to illuminate complex experiences of oppression and inequality and address the exclusionary nature of traditional policy methods (Hankivsky/Jordan-Zachery 2019; Smooth 2013). More specifically, an intersectional approach provides a remedy to policies that adopt the “one size fits all” approach by focusing on a single axis of oppression, or the additive approach whereby policymakers start with a single identity category and build from there without adequately examining how categories are mutually constituted. As Smooth (2013) states, “the deeply entrenched, institutionalized understandings of inequality as existing along a singular axis” presents challenges to employing intersectionality in institutional and policy contexts (ibid., 35).

It is critical to ensure that intersectionality is used to critique assimilationist logics rather than perpetuate them when using it as a tool to inform and shape policies. May (2015) argues that, “Invoking intersectionality to endorse assimilation is widespread, both in immigration and marriage reform. Analysis of recent LGBT gender and marriage laws in Spain shows how state-level approaches to intersectionality can “lack a multiple discrimination perspective” and lean toward assimilation” (ibid., 154). She (ibid.) also highlights despite claiming their use of intersectionality, many European Union member states are complicit in “pitting ‘diversity’ strategies against gender mainstreaming;” for example, by seeing racialized and immigrant others as a threat to gender equality (ibid., 155). Such applications of intersectionality by state institutions “could augment rather than contest the state’s inclination for classifying and categorizing citizens (and noncitizens), thereby facilitating population surveillance, control, and containment” (ibid., 157).

Despite risks of the co-opting and flattening intersectionality in institutional contexts, it remains a valuable tool for building social-justice oriented institutions and structures. This would be achievable if intersectionality becomes a tool of questioning and disrupting hegemonic logics rather

one that maintains the status quo. The next section focuses on youth and participation, examining how an intersectional perspective requires a reconceptualization of the two categories and their relationship.

3. Intersectional Perspectives on Youth and Participation

Because the voting age is 18 in most European countries, young people are largely excluded from their political participation structures and, hence, hardly addressed as political subjects (from political parties, the state or political institutions). Their construction as the adult citizens of tomorrow simultaneously results in the absence of young people from political participation being considered an important problem to address. Therefore, many youthwork-oriented organizations, platforms and social practices address political participation in different ways.

Any effort to address including youth in deliberative and participatory processes must begin with the construction of the “youth” category itself. As the previous sections on intersectionality illustrate, the meanings of categories such as gender, race, class, sexuality, and disability are socially constructed and vary across time and space. Childhood and youth are widely believed to be bounded and discrete categories that are defined by age. However, childhood and youth studies scholars have argued that these categories are socially constructed (Katz 2008; Stockton 2009; Meiners 2016) and that the notion of that childhood, adolescence, and youth as distinct life stages is historically recent (Hartinger-Saunders 2008; Ruddick 2003; Tambe 2019). Childhood and youth emerged as *social*, *moral* and *political* categories through processes of colonialism, gendered capitalism, and globalization, and have been central to ‘civilizing’ and ‘developmental’ projects that helped justify ongoing colonial and racial (gendered) violence (Bernstein 2011; Burman 2008; Pande 2020; Pomfret 2015; Sen 2005). Thus, an intersectional perspective on youth must fundamentally highlight that the ‘youth’ category itself is informed through a (post-)colonial matrix of knowledge and structures, and it interacts with different categories. Consequently, the category has a Eurocentric bias regarding what youth could and should mean and look like, through which youth is specifically constructed.

The youth category continues to attract attention social and political contexts; as Griffin (2001) states, “in racially structured capitalist patriarchal societies, ‘youth’ remains an enormously powerful and resonant cultural symbol which shows few signs of fading” (ibid., 148). One its most enduring constructions sees youth “as a period of inevitable psychological and social turmoil” (ibid., 148). Informed by the work of US psychologist, G. Stanley Hall, western societies have historically translated the “troubled” teen concept into the establishing of institutions and initiatives that manage and control young people, including programs for professional success and stable heterosexual relationships (Griffin 1997, 10). A significant part of managing “troubled” adolescents

and teenagers involves protecting them and excluding them from adult activity, such as labor or politics (Henning 2021, 49). This construction of youth sees 'defiance' and 'rebellion' as "inevitable consequences of youth"; however, "such 'defiance' is viewed through a lens of race and class as well as gender and sexuality" (Griffin 1997, 9-10).

Another critical element of youth and identity categories is that power structures promote developing a supposedly 'stable' identity as a core requirement for young people. Thus, an intersectional perspective should ask if 'identity politics' push against or normalize 'identity positions'.

However, these histories are erased when bourgeois, Western ideals of childhood and youth continue being seen as 'natural' and universal (Balagopalan 2002; Burman 2008). Burman (2008) argues that developmental theories and practices, including those from psychology and economics, have played a crucial role in occluding the diversity and complexity of children and young people's lives and reducing them into singular and universal ideals. For example, the association between childhood and innocence does not only see childhood as a symbol of innocence, but "as its embodiment" (Meiners 2016, 51). Burman notes that images of children that have historically appeared in print media and art have played a key role in securing this idea of childhood, with children "abstracted from social context as a representational cliché of timeless and culture-free innocence" (2008, 14). However, as Meiners (2016) points out, innocence has always been racialized and heterogendered; the disproportionate violence faced by young people of colour highlights that they do not have the same access to innocence as white youth. Despite critiques, the idea of youth and adolescence as a period of "storm and stress" has similarly shaped youth research in psychology, education and sociology; however, this construction is "not ideologically neutral, and it operates along the dimensions of class, gender, sexuality, race, ethnicity and disability, as well as religion and nationality in some instances, to construct marginalized and subordinated groups as the primary source of specific social problems" (Griffin 2001, 149). Approaches to youth that solely view them as defined by age or as a developmental phase fail to account for these complex experiences of marginalization that are produced by these multiple dimensions of power.

An intersectional approach must consider that youth are not just excluded when it comes to intersectional discrimination, but that youth is itself a construction that entails power structures: "Within Western intellectual traditions, there are two dominant conceptions of young people, an angelic one and a demonizing one" (Rooke/Schnell 1983). Notably, the construction of the demonized youth is highly racialized, classed and gendered. This is also visible in how the protest forms of racialized, poor youth are framed: As the 2005 media coverage of French protests revealed, narratives of a demonized youth also invalidated their actions and dismissed the protests as riots rather than legitimate political protest (Hébert 2016, 200).

There is a third pervasive conception that depicts children and youth as consumers, “i.e., as producers, buyers and commodities throughout history, and as buyers in a contemporary market economy” (Hébert 2016, 200). Hébert argues, that this perspective on youth and its underlying expectations are translated into a specific mode of exclusion/inclusion in society. Such a perspective also reveals how each country’s economic system, as well as globalized neoliberal capitalism, affects how ‘normal’ and ‘deviant’ forms of youth and youth participation are constructed: “(I)n the past few years neo-liberal economic policies (...) have created the conditions for mass exclusion of young people from political, economic and social spheres” (Salih/Welchman/Zambelli 2016, 5). According to Salih, Welchman and Zambelli, material resources are key elements for enabling participation. Conversely, impoverished youth are constructed as dangerous youth that ‘require’ governance and surveillance. The construction of the ‘dangerous, poor teenager’ is also racialized and this intersection of race and class serves as legitimization for police surveillance as well as police violence and brutality (Thompson 2021b). Furthermore, youth are substantially excluded from political participation and decision-making in European countries. Racial border regimes and structural racism from police, prison system and legal system materialize themselves in the structural exclusion of the many young people who live in Europe but are either not viewed as full citizens or as citizens at all. Thus, an intersectional approach to the youth category also highlights that not all young people are viewed as ‘youth’: However, being considered a young person can also be a privilege: For example, Black children are often perceived as older than they actually are, which consequently results in their receiving harsher punishment when being criminalized (Bergold-Caldwell 2015, 2020). Young people who are criminalized or framed as ‘dangerous’ or ‘deviant’ others through racism and classism lose the right to being considered youth. Clearly, not everyone is granted the *right to be young* or the right to be considered ‘in development.’ Likewise, these fundamental forms of inclusion and exclusion of certain groups of young people are also highlighted by research on teenage refugees who are also often stripped of their right to be young. Because of its intersection with belonging and not belonging to the state, refugees are also sometimes described as being older than they are, which makes them ineligible for certain forms of state support.

The following section adopts an intersectional approach to underline the complexities of defining the youth category, highlighting how its definitions and experiences intertwine and co-constitute with gender, race, sexuality, class, and disability. Questioning approaches that see childhood and youth as neutral and universal development markers and challenging homogenous ideas of youth is not only the first step in developing more nuanced and complex understandings of young people’s lives, but also critical to advancing a youth-centred vision of social justice. As Burman states, seeing children and young people as a homogenous category has real and damaging effects; “children whose life circumstances and practices of daily living fail to confirm to those

idealised norms suffer further marginalisation, or even pathologisation” (2008, 10). The objective here is not to provide an exhaustive list of categories and structures that shape young people’s experiences since an intersectional lens is not about ‘covering all bases’. Instead, the following sections serve as a starting point for conceptualizing how young people’s social locations shape their experiences of power, including their experiences with participatory and deliberative processes.

3.1 Youth and Spaces of Political Participation

In response to the exclusion of youth from political processes, several European Union countries have established spaces and initiatives for youth political education, participation and deliberation. For instance, the Irish Department of Children and Youth Affairs and local English councils have endorsed the Lundy Model of Child Participation to conceptualise children and young people’s rights to participation, as established in Article 12 of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC). The Lundy Model, developed by Laura Lundy (2007), proposes that successfully implementing Article 12 requires considering four interrelated elements: space, voice, audience and influence.

Space: Children and young people must be given safe, inclusive opportunities to form and express their views.

Voice: Children and young people must be enabled to express their views, which could be imparted orally, in writing or print, through art, or any other desired media.

Audience: The view must be listened to, which ensures young people at least have a ‘right of audience’—a guaranteed opportunity to communicate views to an identifiable individual or body who has a responsibility to listen.

Influence: The view must be acted upon as appropriate. Children and young people should be told what decision was made, how their views were regarded, and the reasons why action has proceeded in that way.

The following section addresses *space*, highlighting spaces that have been created within the European context for young people’s participation. The section highlights how such spaces target youth participation enablement in both formal politics as well as in everyday leisure and cultural activities. However, scholarship that evaluates how effective such spaces are in recognizing and addressing young people’s intersectional experiences with power and inequalities remains absent. Even the Lundy model does not explicitly account for the intersectional nature of barriers to young people’s participation, or offer ways to ensure that awareness of intersectional inequalities is engrained within youth participation and decision-making initiatives and policies. However, they do point, for example, to the first criterion of *space*, which mentions the need for inclusive spaces, and

requires the identification of those we need to target for inclusion. As the next sections highlight, this failure to acknowledge intersectional inequalities is reflected in most spaces that have been created for young people's political participation.

3.1.1 The public

The public sphere is a key place for young people to meet and be among; however, it is also a realm of multiple modes of exclusions. Architecture serves as a fundamental form of exclusion in the public sphere, since public spaces should be places for young people to be and meet—especially in urban areas. However, research shows that this is also a terrain where intersectional marginalization manifests. Thus, an intersectional perspective requires urban planning to also reflect upon these exclusions: “Recognising diverse publics has been an important development, prompting planners and policy makers to reflect on ways their participation practices either implicitly or explicitly exclude certain groups, while privileging others” (Cameron/Grant-Smith 2005, 21). Making the public sphere more inclusive requires reconsidering “factors such as timing, accessibility, provision of childcare, transportation, use of written materials, and presentation style and tone when planning and running public meetings, workshops, forums, visioning exercises and the like (e.g. Sarkissian/Cook/Walsh 1999). Another strategy targets particular groups or communities of interest and provides specific engagement activities within the context of a broader participation program (ibid.): “We therefore argue that recognition of difference needs to be taken a step further so that participatory planning practice contributes to a transformative politics of difference” (ibid.).

Besides the forms of exclusion that arise from material public architecture, research has highlighted multiple forms of subtle exclusion. The public sphere is structured around an ideal citizen who is not only an adult-citizen, but also white, heteronormative, male and abled-bodied. Thus, the question to whom the public sphere belongs and whose actions in the public sphere are considered appropriate, as ‘political’, as ‘disturbing’ also mirrors norms and structures of inequality.

3.1.2 Civic Education in Schools and Universities

Eurydice Brief states that political and civic education, or citizenship education is a priority at the European level, as reflected in the European Commission's Education and Training 2020 Working Group on “Promoting citizenship and the common values of freedom, tolerance and non-discrimination through education” (De Coster/Sigalas 2018). Citizenship education is a subject area that seeks to foster “the harmonious co-existence and mutually beneficial development of individuals and of the communities they are part of. In democratic societies citizenship education supports students in becoming active, informed and responsible citizens, who are willing and able to take responsibility for themselves and for their communities at the local, regional, national and

international level” (ibid., 9). Thus, civic education seeks to both educate children and young people about different political structures and perspectives and increase their political participation, with an assumed correlation between civic education and political participation.

According to the Eurydice Brief 2017, “Encouraging students to participate is present in the curricula of most European educational systems. Thus, modern citizenship education in Europe tends not simply to disseminate theoretical knowledge on democracy, but also to encourage students to become active citizens who participate in public and political affairs” (ibid., 57). This is reflected in the curricula of countries like Greece and Austria that have modules on “participating in school and out-of-school activities” and “media and political participation” being part of the curricula respectively (ibid., 33-37). Student councils are a commonly implemented structure at schools for encouraging young people’s involvement in political processes. For example, Finnish law requires schools to have student body councils that ensure young people’s inclusion and involvement. Integrating student councils with other parliament structures is intended to create spaces for young people to have debate and dialogue. A recent initiative in this regard is the Citizens’ Parliament, which Finland launched in 2023 as a collaboration between Åbo Akademi University, Tampere University, a think-tank and the Finnish parliament.

European schools and universities have sought to implement diverse methods to ensure young people’s civic education and participation. For instance, Youth-led Participatory Action Research (Y-PAR) has been evaluated by students and teachers in Italy using a mixed-method evaluation. They found it effectively fosters the social inclusion of different student groups to different school classes by reducing learning differences and transforming learning competencies towards civic and democratic competencies that can be shared and deployed in a team. Implementing Y-PAR in school settings enhances student participation in researching social issues that affect them, including migration and socio-economic inequalities, enabling them to cultivate a critical understanding of these issues.

Despite several political and civic education initiatives, the link between education and participation remains tenuous. Manning and Edwards (2014) argue that no evidence exists that civic education has a significant effect on voting or increasing normative political participation. Additionally, exclusions within such institutions like of racial, ethnic, gender and sexual minorities, raises the question of how effective they can be in fostering political participation among youth. Here, the difference between civic education, political education and activism becomes relevant. As Mirshak states, political education is about “developing critical consciousness of the existing political, economic and socio-cultural conditions, and seeks to challenge them” (2020, 916). Likewise, political education “take(s) place across many sites in civil society; and provide(s) a broad notion of educators” (ibid). This necessitates recognizing a broader arena of political action, including protest movements that young people are part of, as spaces of political education and participation.

3.1.3 Youth Work, Social Work, and Youth participation

Youth work is “a broad term covering a wide variety of activities of a social, cultural, educational, environmental and/or political nature by, with and for young people, in groups or individually” that has been identified by the Council of Europe for “facilitating young people’s active participation and inclusion in their communities and in decision making” (Council of Europe 2017). Its objectives include young people’s civic and political education and participation as well as the social inclusion of marginalized young people.

Formal and informal institutions that seek to enable youth participation include civil society organizations like youth clubs, cultural organizations and sports clubs. In German and Austrian cities, some youth clubs try to address existing inequalities by helping young migrant people, poor youth or youth who have nowhere to go to organize their daily lives. Young people can do their homework and get help with solving problems, receive food, and receive help with talking to friends and family.

Such spaces also allow young people to develop their own participation initiatives, with several European initiatives that encourage youth to engage in volunteering; for instance, the European Solidarity Corps, an EU programme that “creates opportunities for young people to volunteer, work, train and run their own solidarity projects that benefit communities around Europe” (Williamson et al 2021, 118).

3.1.4 Young People’s Use of Social Media

Contemporary scholarship on young people’s political participation highlights that young people seamlessly move between online and offline spaces in how they express and organize themselves politically, engaging with different spaces and platforms according to their political goals and audiences. In their research on young people’s activism in Spain, Estonia and the United Kingdom, Charles et al. (2018) find that activist groups have different repertoires of action, combining the use of social media with older forms of organizing. For instance, Feminist Indignades, a feminist group based in Spain, used social media to spread information about their activities while also drawing on the legacies of older Spanish feminist movements to protest the gendered impacts of the 2008 economic crisis as well as the prevalence of sexism in Spanish society. The group also engages in “transgressive actions ranging from street performances to the occupation of underground trains,” seeing these actions as “challenging the heteronormative-capitalist-patriarchal framework” (ibid., 11). The authors also emphasize the central role of emotions to the activist interventions they study, stating that “friendship and emotional ties cement solidarity within movement networks and contribute to the creation of a community of interests and collective identity” (ibid., 23).

In their research on FridaysforFuture (FFF) – Rome, a climate activism movement by young people in Rome, Belotti et al. (2022) also find that young activists move between online and offline spaces, without a rigid distinction between the two. Participants in their study see social media as ‘their own thing’ (ibid., 727) and use it to reach out to younger audiences, a cohort they see as being most affected by climate change. The young activists also use social media to “reach other social organizations, such as the student movement in Rome, BlackLivesMatter (an international anti-racist movement in defense of black communities), NonUnaDiMeno (an Italian feminist movement against gender-based violence), and all associations dealing with ecological issues in the Italian capital city” (ibid., 730). In doing so, the young FFF – Rome movement activists “articulate trans-local alliances and intersect their struggles” (ibid., 730). These can be analyzed as an instance of political intersectionality, whereby young activists conceptualize climate justice as linked to larger struggles for social justice.

Social media platforms are increasingly recognised for expanding avenues of deliberative and political participation, with the internet portrayed as a democratizing space that can enable participatory practices. Scholars such as James and Cotnam-Kappel (2020) have highlighted how social media platforms “are venues for 24/7 political discussion – including deliberation, everyday banter, and bickering. For youth, these platforms offer new opportunities and risks for participation, and suggest corresponding implications for civic education.” Young people’s use of digital technologies and policymakers’ assumptions of online spaces as facilitating democratic and non-hierarchical public spheres has led to “significant public discussion of, and investment in, E-democracy solutions to the problem of young people’s reluctance to engage in traditional political participation, in particular, voting” (Pilkington/Pollock 2015, 4). In Finland, the Ministry of Justice has founded several online channels for youth participation, including Digiraati.fi, where participants under the age of 29 are invited to discuss social issues. These discussion events can be organized by ministries, municipalities, or other organizations for free and participants are directly invited.

Elsewhere, the OurSpace project sought to improve European youth engagement with European policymakers through information and communication technologies. In Parycek et al.’s (2014) evaluation, they found European youth capable of “to engag[ing] in face-to-face and anti-hierarchical discussions with both politicians and other users, and [engaging] in respectful and inclusive deliberation online” (ibid., 138).

Despite using social media as a space for political participation, young people’s use of such spaces comes with its own set of challenges. Baek et al. (2012) find that compared to face-to-face deliberation, online deliberation over-represents young, male, and white users, attracts more ideological moderates, generates more negative emotions, and is less likely to result in consensus and political action. Pilkington and Pollock argue that young people’s use of social media is

characterized by “ambivalence” and “tension,” with young activists expressing concerns around state surveillance and the ‘careless’ use of social media (2015, 6).

Questioning the assumption of online spaces as being untouched by racist, heterosexist, and patriarchal structures is critical to understanding the potential for digital technologies and online spaces to foster youth participation. Feminist theorizing on online spaces highlights that the promise of digital equality through technical progress has not been realized, especially for those who experience intersectional forms of discrimination. Violence against marginalized groups in online spaces, including gendered and sexualized forms of violence against women, often leads to them choosing not to participate on social media (Subramanian 2015, 2019). In their study of hate speech on North Belgian blogs, Cammaerts (2009) analyzes how extreme right groups invoke their right to freedom of speech to propagate hate and violence against immigrants, people of colour, and other marginalized groups. Their research highlights that the very accessibility of online spaces that make it appealing as a tool for fostering deliberation and democracy also makes it a space that propagates violence against marginalized groups.

Thus, James and Cotnam-Kappel (2020) propose that using the internet and social media as a realm of participation in deliberative and political discussions requires investing in “civic education” for youth. Here they recommend using youth conceptions of good online dialogue and its key ingredients—knowledge, respect, and diversity— “as resources” (ibid.). Thus, civic education and participation issues must address social media as a simultaneous mode of participation and exclusion.

3.2 Youth and Dimensions of Exclusions

Despite the institutionalized spaces for youth political participation described above, young people continue to express low trust in democratic institutions and withdraw from traditional institutional political participation. Their lack of engagement with formal political structures has several implications: It indicates their apathy, is a consequence of engagement in informal and non-institutionalized forms of politics, or results from “a deeper lack of fit between political institutional models and the kinds of concerns expressed by young people, who have grown up in a socioeconomic context of precarity and instability” (Pilkington/Pollock 2015, 2). For example, the 2022 Italian Parliament renewal reflects forms of exclusion inherent to existing institutions of political participation wherein setbacks for indicators regarding the inclusion of women and youth in national political representation highlighted the marked disadvantage for the latter in the current legislative term.

Young people’s lack of engagement with existing spaces and youth participation initiatives raises questions of whether they can capture the complexities of their lives, which underlines the importance of an intersectional approach to young people’s lives and experiences. As Grasso and

Giugni state, “The worry here is that, if young people have little knowledge about the political processes and distrust politicians in their abilities to address their issues of concern, then the foundations of democracy may further deteriorate in the future. Worse still, if young people from more socially disadvantaged backgrounds are less likely than those who are more well off to engage politically and to have positive attitudes with respect to politics, then this means that those most in need of political voice to redress current imbalances of power in democratic societies are further silenced” (2022, 15). The following sections adopt an intersectional perspective to highlight the complex experiences and negotiations with power that inform young people’s everyday experiences, which questions whether existing youth participation initiatives are attentive to these complexities.

3.3 Identity politics and Research on Intersectional Identity

First and foremost, the question of whether a social identity is a marker of political struggles around participation or a marker for a marginalized position remains a matter of debate. As Moffit at al. state “intersectional research can help shed light on precisely this issue, namely by examining how individuals are making sense of and pushing against the boundaries of ostensibly neutral and static social identity categories created in the past decades in the absence of ‘race’” (2020, 2). However, intersectional research asks what specific role identity categories and their intersections play in youth development because young people are more likely to face the normative requirement and social expectation to develop what is assumed as a ‘stable’ identity. Thus, an intersectional perspective on identity categories and politics scrutinizes if ‘identity politics’ serve as broadening or restricting agency; In other words, if youth push back against normalized and excluding ‘identity positions’ or if identity politics can help develop an emancipatory form of identity? Azmitia and Mansfield ask the following questions that are relevant for any intersectional research on youth and identity categories: “(1) Who is included in a social identity category? And are there diversity levels of within-group variability in social identity, such as gender, race, class, or sexuality? When does the dissimilarity between group members render the identity category incoherent? (2) What roles do inequality and oppression play in the construction of identity intersectionality?” (2021, 2). Hence, this reminds researchers “to continue Crenshaw’s discussion around inequality in the legal system, concentrating on how power and oppression contextualize youth’s daily lives” (ibid.). They propose “problematiz[ing] the construct of multiple jeopardy, i.e., that the more minority identities youth have, the more powerless they will feel in contemporary society” because these “multiple minoritized identities (can also) serve as a source of pride and power for youth, particularly those engaged in social activism” (ibid.). Likewise, Gordon and Taft (2011) point out the importance of youth political activism to transform experiences of intersectional exclusions into empowering modes of intersectional identity politics. They also stress the importance of youth who experience

multiple forms of discrimination acting as role models, which Griffiths (2024) also emphasizes by referring to political participation through young disabled people's 'identity politics': "Understanding disabled youth activism is key for improving young disabled people's participation in politics and social change. Young disabled people require opportunities to situate historical and biographical experiences within broader socioeconomic contexts" (2024, 83). Here, youth political activism offers the potential to gain control over disadvantages, discrimination and build an 'emancipatory' identity that is based on self-representation (Terriquez 2015).

This framing of identity categories and politics as ambivalent—both restricting and enabling—allows an intersectional perspective to ask how this double-sided approach can also serve as a starting point for youth alliances that vary in their social identities. As Azmitia and Mansfield ask: "Are there similarities in the intersectional experiences of youth who vary in their social identities? For example, is there a common ground for youth who experience different identity configurations and oppressions?" (2021, 2). This has implications for how to think 'intersectionally' in terms of youth identity development and psychology.

Which categories are in interplay and how do they affect participation?

The following section discusses forms of normative frameworks and exclusions in youth development of youth that arise from multiple forms of structures of oppression. We highlight how identity categories serve as modes of restriction, but also provide youth who experience marginalization with the potential to form coalitions and exercise their political agency. An intersectional perspective on youth must acknowledge the social context and thus, the powerful dynamics, complexities, and structures of identity categories and their potential for exclusion. Each category has its risks, with people experiencing different types of discrimination.

3.2.1 Class and youth

The global economic crisis has profoundly impacted young people in Europe, and has been followed by a dramatic increase in their unemployment rates across EU member states. Drawing on existing research about European youth, Fahmy states that youth—particularly those who have left their childhood homes—are more vulnerable to income poverty than older working-age adults (2014, 38). She explains, "Despite some significant variations across European societies as a result of institutional and social differences, globalisation appears to have intensified the effects of educational and class inequalities in shaping labour market risks and outcomes for young people, resulting in increased employment uncertainty and postponed family formation" (ibid., 40). While EU policies have sought to address youth unemployment, labour market interventions alone are unlikely sufficient to insulate young Europeans from the risk of poverty and social exclusion (Fahmy 2014, 42).

Young people's social and material deprivation is also visible in their political organizing and participation. Following the financial crisis, young people have organized around class, especially concerning the right to free education as well as against austerity measures and global capitalism, as seen in the Occupy movement. For instance, 283 out of 420 higher education institutions in Greece were occupied by students protesting against neoliberal reforms to higher education in 2011 (Lidan 2013, 368).

However, deepening class inequalities also have a significant effect on young people's political engagement, as Grasso and Giugni (2022)'s study of youth political engagement across nine European countries (France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Poland, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and the United Kingdom) shows. They find that class inequalities significantly impact youth engagement with multiple political participation activities, including participation in demonstrations, attending political organization or party meetings, community service participation and online activism. They state, "With respect to democratic attitudes, we can see that there are significant class differences in a majority of the countries with respect to the idea that democracy may have problems but it is better than any other form of government with people from lower class backgrounds being less positive about democracy in this respect" (2022, 31). The economic and political crises experienced by youth and their resulting disillusionment with electoral politics have had diverse consequences; for instance, younger people in Germany increasingly support smaller parties over the two largest parties, while young men from less privileged backgrounds in countries like Greece and France are being drawn to far-right groups (Sloam 2014, 223).

Research on youth poverty reveals that the complexity of the relationship between economic deprivation and social and material deprivation (Fahmy 2014). Austerity politics and the resulting effects of unemployment and precarity have led to mass emigration—including within Europe, such as with Greek youth migrating to Cyprus (Chatzipanagiotidou 2018). Although emigration was used as a strategy by Greek youth for professional advancement, they once again experienced precarity as Cyprus later experienced its own economic crisis (Chatzipanagiotidou 2018, 237). These diverse experiences of economic and material precarity show the need for more nuanced analytical frameworks, with Collins and Bilge asserting that economic inequality cannot be assessed through class alone and that "intersectionality proposes a more sophisticated map of social inequality that goes beyond class-only accounts" (2016, 16). As the following sections highlight, multiple factors, including experiences of disability and migration, can further compound the precarities experienced by youth of lower-class backgrounds.

3.2.2 Youth and Experiences of Gender

Most interventions that target youth implicitly assume young men as the object of public action (Salih/Welchman/Zambelli 2016, 6). As Salih, Welchman and Zambelli state, "The "institutional

invisibility” of “young women” in public discourse rests on and reflects a specific framing of “young women” as both vulnerable and dangerous subjects who are mainly defined by their sexuality and who, accordingly, ought to be protected and confined within their familiar and maternal roles (i.e., as daughters, wives and mothers)” (ibid.).

However, racialized, classed and ableist constructions of sexuality mean that not all young women are considered worthy of protection. In her study on legal standards for girls’ sexual maturity in India, Tambe (2019) highlights how sexual age standards are not only defined differently for girls and boys, but that these standards have varied across nation-states and shifted across time. She highlights how climatological accounts were used by colonizers from Western Europe to claim that girls in tropical climates attained sexual maturity at a younger age. Such beliefs around the sexual precocity of girls were used to justify the implementation of lower ages of consent in the colonies, thereby placing these girls outside of state protection. Tambe’s (ibid.) work highlights how the category of girlhood, which is often assumed to be a category only marked by age and gender, has had varied meanings across geographies and over time. These variations also reflect colonial workings at multiple scales and highlight how colonial discourses and practices of power shaped how girls experienced their bodies and sexualities.

As decolonial feminists have demonstrate, the gender category is largely a result of the coloniality of power (Quijano 2000), with María Lugones (2007, 2010) referring to it as a colonial category (Lugones 2007, 2010, 2016). Likewise, African feminists have stressed the coloniality of the gender (Abbas/Ekine 2013; Oyěwùmí 1997) and a Eurocentric concept of queerness (Abbas/Ekine 2013; Bollwinkel 2017). Likewise, a critical disability perspective reveals the gender category’s limitations and restrictions since people with disabilities are excluded from the gender binary and heterosexual matrix of desire (Schildmann 2003).

Discourses that mark girls with sexual vulnerability also contradict their girls’ experiences of race and nationality, as illustrated by Keaton’s (2006) research on the experiences of Muslim girls of African origins living in French outer cities. The work underscores the many levels of violence that these women face in a context where they are “neither immigrants nor foreigners” but “have been convenient scapegoats for many social ills” (2006, 193). Keaton highlights how Muslim youth of African origins are blamed for issues like increased violence, high unemployment, and low-performing schools; they are segregated and confined in French public housing in outer cities and in “ghettoized schooling,” with disadvantaged youth concentrated in the most disadvantaged schools (ibid., 194). The violence experienced by young Muslim women of African origin—especially those who wear a veil—is compounded by how the structures of French law and schooling construct the veil as “anti-secular” and “anti-French.” Girls who refuse to remove their

head coverings can be expelled according to a 2004 law that bans “the wearing of signs and dress manifesting a religious affiliation in the elementary, middle, and high schools” (ibid., 179). This law “contributes to young women’s stigmatization and social exclusion”, “reducing girls’ life chances in a credential-driven society” (ibid., 183). Additionally, young Muslim women must contend with issues of shame and honour that are used to justify the community surveillance of their bodies, movements, and actions. As Keaton (ibid.) argues, young Muslim women in France “must also develop strategies to cope and exist within often incompatible arenas, sometimes to their own peril. These circumstances make the politics of their existence highly complex and in some ways unique” (ibid., 195). This work raises the question of whether spaces of schools and universities foster political education and participation without examining how these spaces are complicit in excluding marginalized youth, including young people of colour, queer youth, and disabled youth.

When reflecting on the relevance of gender for youth in current societies, it is also important to take into account that according to the dominant discourses gender is not viewed as a relevant category anymore. Angela McRobbie (2016) has coined the notion “postfeminist” to describe the current era as characterized through the following dynamics: there is an endeavour for gender equality and young girls face a narrative that gender no longer has relevance and that they can achieve anything, they must also distance themselves from being feminists or having feminist opinions. By emphasizing this contradiction, McRobbie also shows the normative framework and double standards that girls are confronted with. Despite the growing popularity of feminist ideas among young people, quite often this only serves as rhetoric since structural inequalities are not addressed (see also Spiers 2018). Rather, girls and young women must solve these problems alone, on a personal level.

Growing up or being a teenager in a post-feminist era implies the silencing of gendered structures and dominant discourses that center the narrative that implies that contemporary women live in a fully self-responsible manner. Thus, women are expected to live independent lives while simultaneously having a stable partnership, kids and/or family (McRobbie 2016; Krüger-Kirn 2017). Women face double standards of being able to have sex lives, be sexually open, and not romantically attached, which allows them the freedom to pursue a career. At the same time, young parenthood (i.e., before turning 30) is highly undesirable in Western societies and falls under specific controls (McRobbie 2013, 2014). Postfeminist girls and young women are described as sexually open, but the legacy of gendered, patriarchal norms still restricts their access to open and joyful sexual behavior. While the opportunity for sexual openness is considered a necessary and taken-for-granted characteristic for white girls, a gendered and racialized, postcolonial legacy conversely depicts girls of colour and Muslim girls as not-yet-sexually-open (Bergold-Caldwell 2015, 2020).

Furthermore, an intersectional perspective reveals another contradiction for young women and girls of colour as well as of the Muslim religion that shapes their gendered development: Although Western European societies are far from achieving substantial gender equality, a discourse has emerged in recent decades that believes gender equality has already been attained. This postfeminist narrative is used at a discursive level to construct Europe as the epitome of progress and to 'prove' Europe's exceptionalism (Dietz 2013; Dietze 2017). Thus, 'femonational' and 'homonational' discourses" (Farris 2017; Puar 2007; Dhawan 2015) serve as discourses against immigrants, who are constructed as lacking a willingness to support gender and sexual equality (Rodriguez/Winkel/Tuzcu 2017). Femonational and homonational discourses also shape the discursive context of marginalized female youth in Europe.

Gender and gender rationalities categories are highly critical when discussing care (Winker 2011), care equality or democracy (Tronto 2013), or reproductive justice (Kitchen Politics 2021). Having equal rights in an unequal society—especially when involving care and care equality—interacts with young people as children, teenagers, and young adults. It concerns their future, especially their willingness to be in relationships and be accountable, in a society that is informed by neoliberal understandings of relationships and partnering.

3.2.3 Being young and LGBTIQ

The normative connotation of sexual and gender identities is that they are singular, static, and 'stable' during a person's lifetime and not meant to change. Despite critiques of such heteronormative discourses by queer theorists like Butler (2012), Halberstam (2018), and Rodriguez (2002), as well as decolonial theorists such as Lugones (2007), these ideas continue to inform laws and policies. Given the construction of children and youth as 'innocent' and the erasure of their voices and opinions, they are considered especially vulnerable to "gender mania" (Schmincke 2015). Queer youth remain vulnerable to institutionalized forms of violence and exclusion, which shape their social and material conditions. Discourses that harm LGBTIQ youth are reflected in school programs as well as in conservative, right-wing, and extreme-right discourses, such as "Manif pour tous" in France and "Demo für alle" in Germany (Grenz 2021; Kettlehut 2018). Acts of violence and exclusion against LGBTIQ youth are also reproduced within other movements, such as highly stigmatizing trans-exclusionary 'feminist' discourses (Worthen 2022).

LGBTIQ youth experiences are further shaped by their social locations and their interactions with other power structures, which demonstrates the vital importance of an intersectional perspective. As Coleman-Fountain (2020) states, disabled young people's experiences are often omitted from conversations and initiatives concerning LGBTIQ youth. Drawing on a study conducted in northeast England with gay and lesbian youth on their identity narratives, Coleman-Fountain

(2020) illustrates how being disabled further compounds LGBTIQ youths' feeling of being a "misfit;" for example, through name-calling and prejudice. They suggest considering how "inhospitality might entail more than a relation to heteronormativity but to forms of ableism that also structure relations to the norm and access to discourses of 'normality' and 'ordinariness'" (ibid., 103). Coleman-Fountain (2020) argues that paying attention to the complex and intersecting issues that confront youth offers an alternative to emerging narratives of normalization in LGBT youth research.

In terms of LGBTQ youth activism, Terriquez's (2015) research on LGBTIQ participation in the undocumented immigrant youth movement in California offers a theoretical framework for understanding how social movements can help members of disadvantaged subgroups attain leadership roles. The results show how LGBTQ activists encountered significant barriers to disclosing their sexual orientation, even as they were more civically engaged than their straight and cis-gendered peers. However, the immigrant youth movement's adoption of the LGBTQ movement's strategy of "coming out" – that is of becoming visibly and reclaiming rights – empowered undocumented youth around both their legal status and sexual orientation. As Terriquez states, "At the organizational level, multi-identity work that addressed activists' overlapping identities created inclusive environments for LGBTQ members. Finally, at the individual level, LGBTQ undocumented youth exhibited an intersectional consciousness regarding the multiple forms of oppression they experienced; this, in turn, intensified their activism" (2015, 343).

3.2.4 Disability and young people's experiences of political participation

Bjørn et al (2014) argue that people with disabilities people have weak or no representation in policymaking bodies, leading to their general interests—and more specifically, their agency and exercise of citizenship—being largely absent from the political agenda (7). Policies such as Article 26 of the 2000 Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, which "recognises and respects the right of persons with disabilities to benefit from measures designed to ensure their independence, social and occupational integration and participation in the life of the community" (European Union Charter 2012, 400) seek to protect the right to active citizenship for people with disabilities. Nevertheless, "meta- or pre-political factors, factors related to institutional or policy design, and factors related to the implementation of relevant policy" prevent disabled people from exercising active citizenship (Bjørn et al 2014, 6). Likewise, people with psychosocial disabilities or mental illnesses face specific barriers to political participation. For example, people with mental illnesses can have their voting rights restricted by the state in Germany and Switzerland (Lindqvist et al. 2017, 114).

Disabled children and young people often face barriers to their political participation at multiple sites, including education. As Sainsbury et al. (2017) find, structural and relational barriers prevent young people with disabilities from entering upper secondary or further education (ibid., 92). In terms of tertiary educational attainment rates, Ireland and United Kingdom have particularly large gaps between those with and without disabilities, which has implications for the former's employment. Despite policies aimed to improve employment rates, the disability employment gap remains high across Europe (Sainsbury et al. 2017, 104). Since the 2008 financial crisis, the labour market has been especially competitive and hostile for young people with disabilities. These structural disadvantages are further compounded for youth who are migrants and disabled, with Waddington (2017) stating that, "migrants were less likely than nationals to receive disability or unemployment benefits" (ibid., 207).

3.2.5 Youth, Ethnicity, Race and the Nation

While efforts to increase political participation target youth as 'citizens in the making,' their lived experiences—especially of those who experience multiple, intersecting forms of marginalization—are marked by feeling unseen, unheard, and—significantly—as not belonging. In this regard, structures and experiences of national or European citizenship become sites where young people experience othering and exclusion.

The category of the nation state is one that is built through exclusions (Bergold-Caldwell/Ludwig 2024; Foucault 2003; Ludwig 2015; Sauer 2001). Belonging to the nation state must be constantly articulated and performed (Ludwig 2015); however, this performance is only available to those who are imagined and legalized as citizens of a state. In several nation states, including Germany, the imagination of a citizen and its legalization fall along racial lines (El-Tayeb 2016). Until early 2000, German citizenship was based upon the bloodline (*Ius sanguinis*), as with many European countries like Austria. Racial and ethnic minorities experience discrimination and exclusion at both the structural levels and the everyday and interpersonal experience levels. Hence, stereotyping racial and ethnic minorities informs and works alongside their material and social deprivation; for example, the stereotyping of young Black and Muslim men as sexual perpetrators (Bergold-Caldwell/Grubner 2020) rationalizes police and state violence against them. Young people's experiences of exclusion are further complicated by contentions around the race category in the European context. While the structure of race is central to young people's experiences of housing, education, employment, and the criminal justice system, race as a category is also repudiated and invisibilized in several European contexts. When addressing the idea that racism and race-related issues are irrelevant in the European context, Roig (2007) states that "Race-blindness and post-racialism are highly problematical in a social context where all forms of racism continue to reflect the privileges, positions, and biases of the white dominant population" (613).

Given the forms of violence and exclusion that racial and ethnic minorities face within existing structures and ideas of the nation state, several scholars have investigated how youth political participation might look. For instance, Bečević and Dahlstedt (2022) highlight the socioeconomic and ethnic segregation experienced by youth in Sweden, reflected in factors like which part of the city they live in. The authors state that young people's experienced spatial and economic segregation is especially stark for those with foreign-born parents, with such young people placed "outside of people's conception of the nation, a form of symbolic exclusion tightly intertwined with the spatial and economic" (ibid., 371). Their exclusion is exacerbated by initiatives that target them; for example, through their interactions with social workers who "act colonially" and see them as "leisure time activity" (ibid., 374). Bečević and Dahlstedt (2022) ask what potential for youth participation is available to young working-class ethnic minorities when they are cut off from the city, but also cast outside the imagined nation (ibid., 373). They state, "The feeling of not being part of the Swedish nation is central to understanding participatory practices amongst groups of young people in the suburbs who in most cases are born and raised in Sweden. Feelings of widespread alienation and resentment towards a nation which they perceive to be resentful of them is a crisis of citizenship with negative implications for participation" (ibid., 374). Bečević and Dahlstedt's (2022) work points to the need for addressing the colonial and racist assumptions that undergird existing avenues of youth participation, including targeted social work initiatives. Without addressing such structures of exclusion, these avenues become spaces of alienation rather than participation for young people.

As depicted above, young people's political participation is complicated in a context where forms of exclusion and violence cast them as "not-belonging" to their nation state. Several structures and discourses act together to create contexts of non-belonging for young people who experience intersectional forms of marginalization based on their ethnic, racial, gender, and sexual identities. Young people's experiences of inequalities, exclusions, and oppression and the political strategies that they employ in response reflect the need to reconsider the very definition of politics and what counts as political engagement. The next section turns to deliberative democracy, where we first refer to literature on deliberative democracy and structural intersectional inequalities and then focus on deliberative democracy and youth.

4. Deliberative democracy and structural inequalities

Engagement with deliberative democracy from a critical race theory perspective highlights the following "structural limits of deliberation" (Drake 2023, 96)²: First, a critical race theory perspective

Drake (2023) also points out that these structural shortcomings of deliberation are echoed in the academic literature on deliberative democracy where structural racism of societies and politics is rarely taken into account.

urges us to take the materialist and social conditions of deliberation into account. Instead of arguing from a normative perspective, such a perspective shows the necessity to reflect the material and social accessibility of deliberative processes: “While ideal conditions of deliberative discourse may exist and enable rational consensus among wealthy residents of suburban Frankfurt or Princeton deliberating about the installation of additional streetlights in their neighborhood, it is difficult to imagine how Indigenous communities in the Brazilian Amazon can engage in deliberative discourse as equal citizens with powerful market and state actors intent on expanding mining and logging on Indigenous lands. Even in urban contexts it would be naïve to expect that citizens can participate as equals, respectfully, and exercise their reason freely given the realities of structural inequalities and discriminations based on race, class, gender, and sexual orientation” (Banerjee 2021, 285). Thus, the social foundation of democracy is deeply and structurally unjust (Drake 2023, 100). Structural inequality—not equality—is the basis of democracy (Banerjee 2021; Fung 2005; Gibson 2020, 435; Young 2001). As Drake states: The “ability to engage in democratic activities is profoundly different depending upon which side of whiteness a person finds themselves” (Drake 2023, 100). Thus, substantially changing deliberative democracy requires fundamentally changing the access to forums of deliberation such as public spaces, assemblies, activisms as well as to formal (state) institutions in order to overcome the inherent whiteness of the public sphere, civil society, and political institutions (ibid.)³.

Second, deliberative democracy that aspires to change racist inequalities needs to address structural power relations. Deliberative democracy is not just about improving ‘procedural design,’ but must address structural power relations. A normative approach to power that abstracts from structural power relations “is patently unsatisfactory because it elides relationships between power, legitimacy and authority. How does ‘procedural design’ handle dissent or conflict? And if there is no dissent or conflict in deliberations then has there been an elite capture of the process by excluding or marginalizing dissenting stakeholders?” (Banerjee 2021, 285) Here Banerjee in particular points to the global context and to the violent legacy of colonialism and slavery (ibid., 286–288).

Consequently, third, a critical race theory perspective argues that democracy is not just about inclusion, but also about the willingness to unlearn privileges (Drake 2023, 101). Given that white supremacy has long structured political institutions, political agency and politics, improving the substantive presence of racialized people in deliberative systems alone is insufficient (Beauvais 2018; Smith 2013; Su 2017), because it will prolong structural injustice where Black and other

Here, Drake points to the Black Live Matters protests and states that praise the protests as democratizing activism is insufficient as long as these celebrations omit the need for structural change. “There can be no meaningful deliberative democratic celebration of the system-wide success of BLM protests as long as deliberative systems fail to deal with anti-Black racism as a foundational obstacle to equality.” (Drake 2023 102)

racialized people are systematically devalued. Therefore, the political “willingness of those with power to listen, and give sufficient weight to, the critiques of people experiencing oppression” (Drake 2023, 103) becomes a crucial element of deliberative democracy that aims to overcome structural racism. Hence, deliberation in a structurally unjust society also entails shifting the responsibility for change from marginalized people to those who are privileged (Drake 2023, 106) and inducing processes that promote learning to listen to those who are marginalized as a vital democratizing element (ibid.).

Fourth, a critical race theory perspective highlights the need to reshape forms of deliberation. As long as structural racialized inequalities exist, they will be accompanied by a structural lack of reciprocity (Hooker 2009) that must be addressed and politicized as a crucial element of deliberation (Drake 2023, 94). Consequently, a race critical perspective reveals the need to reshape the centrism of consensus since consensus can only occur at the price of racial aphasia, and thus, at a “collective inability to speak about race” (Thompson 2013, 135). Therefore, deliberative democracy must make race a key political notion, with Drake proposing: “Make anti-racism part of deliberative design” (ibid., 104). This also implies *addressing* structural inequalities and whiteness instead of silencing them (ibid., 105). As discussed earlier, a postcolonial approach, anti-racist approach stresses the need to decenter consensus and focus on how democracy can take antagonisms into account instead of abstracting from them. Furthermore, these approaches—again, in theoretical proximity to approaches of radical democratic theory—argue that democracy must also include conflict as crucial element of democracy instead of focusing solely on consensus.

5. Deliberative democracy, youth and intersectionality

There is scarce research on deliberative democracy, youth and intersectionality. As a first step, we reference literature in the following that addresses the relation between deliberative democracy and youth. Second, we introduce some of the few contributions on deliberative democracy, youth, and intersectionality.

As Zlontnik Raz and Almog (2023, 95) highlight, perceiving and treating children as political citizens is supported by the Children’s Rights Convention and its statements on the rights of children to be heard. However, democratic theory expresses widespread skepticism against the potential for youth participation due to assumptions that children and adolescents lack the necessary political, moral and/or intellectual capacities (Christiano 2001; for a critical stance see Nishiyama 2017, 2). A bias towards a “strong future orientation” instead perceives children and youth as “future citizens” (Nishiyama 2017, 2), rather than already-citizens. This skeptical perspective on youth participation in democracy arises from a specific understanding of children and youth as “empty” beings who need to be prepared for politics and lack political agency due to their age

(Abendschön 2014; Biesta 2011; Kahne et al. 2000). Alanen’s statements in 1980s hold true for democratic theory: “(T)he child remains negatively defined (...), the child is depicted as pre-social, potentially social, in the process of becoming social – essentially undergoing socialization.” (Alanen 1988, 56)

In contrast to this understanding of childhood and youth, a small strand in democratic theory aims to push forward another view of “children as *citizens*” (Fowler 2014, emphasis added). In the past decade, more scholarly awareness has been placed on the role of youth in public decision making and deliberation (Assim 2019; Cockburn 2010; Cook 2013; Zlontnik Raz/Almog 2023), including some scholars (Nishiyama 2017; Zlontnik Raz/Almog 2023) who have explicitly pointed out the potential of deliberative democracy for youth participation. Zlontnik Raz and Almog highlight four reasons why deliberative democracy has the inherent potential to be extended to children and youth: First, their participation is a matter of fulfilling deliberative democracy’s ideal of inclusion (2023, 92). This normative goal of deliberative democracy of inclusion requires overcoming “unique barriers to participation in terms of access and meaningful participation (age-based restrictions; need for parental consent; ‘age-blind’ mechanisms that are not designed for or adapted to children, etc.)” (Zlontnik Raz/Almog 2023, 92–93) must become a task of democracy itself. Notably, Zlontnik Raz and Almog stress the relevance of children’s heterogeneity of children in this context, although without little clarification about what this would entail. Second, opening up deliberative democracy for youth, “fulfills the *epistemic/educational* aim of deliberative democracy which seeks to enhance civic knowledge and promote the (re-)engagement of citizens in democracy” (ibid., 93). Third, children’s participation in deliberative democracy is crucial because it enables “more informed decision-making” (ibid.). This argument rests upon the premise that children and youth are the experts of their own lives. Fourth, youth participation is vital for deliberative democracy since young people do not usually have any legal, economic or political (i.e. institutionalized) form of power; hence, turning to deliberative forums like the public sphere is their only way to be heard as political actors (ibid.).

In her ‘manifesto’ on youth and deliberative democracy, Nishiyama argues in favour of supporting the need to expand deliberative democracy to youth and emphasises the potential of their participation along three dimensions: First, viewing children and youth as citizens expands the realm of political actors. Existing research demonstrates that youth should not only be integrated into already-existing—albeit adult-centered—forms of participation. Rather, the democratic potential of youth participation lies precisely in the “potential role of the “outsiders” of the specific democratic forum, who may be involved in democracy in a different way” (Nishiyama 2017, 10). “A number of projects have been designed for this purpose in the form of, for example, child congress, community planning, consultative forum, or child-led youth parliament (...). However, focusing intensively on these projects sometimes narrows the potential contribution of children. This is

because this framework can recognize children as citizens only when they are recruited by adults to participate in the specific democratic activities and to engage actively with the selected and substantive issues (Kallio, 2012). Such projects and the underlying 'children as citizens' framework appreciate only limited and/or exceptional children's involvement in democracy." (Nishiyama 2017, 10) Truly grasping children as citizens implies the potential to go beyond a universal understanding of democratic participation and communication and to radically expand the forms of democracy and democratic agenda setting and democratic deliberation.

Second, in relation to the first dimension, seeing children and youth as citizens also expands the spaces of democracy (Nishiyama 2017), which places the potential of youth democracy fully in line with that of deliberative democracy. As authors like Fraser have elaborated, deliberative democracy requires a plurality of democratic spaces. By not subsuming youth participation under adult-centric pathways, it can also open up the spaces of democracy and e.g. include everyday practices like school forums as part of democratic deliberation.

Third, Nishiyama notes that opening up democracy for youth also expands the democratic scope, meaning that deliberation would refer to both the present and future impacts of political decisions. She underscores this by describing how: "(i)n 1999, for example, more than 600 children from more than 100 countries gathered in Hawaii to participate in The Millennium Young People's Congress supported by the United Nations. In this congress, children discussed and assessed issues for their future (e.g. education, peace-building, HIV/AIDS); shared experiences; and determined strategies for the globalized world. As a part of the outcome of the five-day discussion, they decided to establish Be The Change. This is a child-led sustainable development action program, aimed at providing funding for small-sized community improvement projects in developing countries or areas that contribute to the sustainable development all over the world, such as a water supply project in Tanzania" (ibid., 12).

Thus, the potential of youth participation in deliberative democracies goes beyond expanding the number of political actors, and includes transforming how doing deliberation and doing democracy in a radical way is conceived. An approach that avoids pigeon-holing children and youth into adult-centered frames as well as forms of participation and deliberation would indeed allow youth participation to make democracy more democratic by shifting well-established forms of agenda-settings or decision-making. Seeing youth as democratic citizens allows for acknowledging these 'outsiders' as effective agents of democracy by focusing on how they contribute to and enhance the overall quality of the deliberative system. In other words, the deliberative system provides room to incorporate and account for children's unique democratic involvement, even if their individual activity does not always have a real influence on official policy actions. For example, although "(p)rotesting may not have a direct influence on decision-making in the official discourse or solve a public problem immediately (...), children's protests have the potential to vitalize deliberations as

a systemic whole in ways, for example, that trigger adults' public deliberation, bring previously unnoticed children's voices to the wider public, or alter the preferences of adults who represent children" (Nishiyama 2017, 10-11).

Gordon and Taft highlight the importance of teenage social activists who can serve as role models for other young people (Gordon/Taft 2011). This is a good example of a democratizing mode of re-adapting identity politics because marginalized teenager activists simultaneously make structures of exclusion visible and act as role models. Similarly, Griffiths (2024) focuses on youth with disabilities to expand the potential of identity politics, which again demonstrates the double importance of inducing political change by revealing structures of inclusion. This highlights potential approaches to re-writing individual and group identity: "Understanding disabled youth activism is key for improving young disabled people's participation in politics and social change. Young disabled people require opportunities to situate historical and biographical experiences within broader socioeconomic contexts" (ibid.). Also, Griffiths' paper discusses activism as a form of taking control over disadvantages, discrimination and gaining a 'good' identity (see also Terriquez 2015).

An intersectional perspective raises a few questions regarding the potential of youth participation for deliberative democracy: How is 'outsider' position structurally shaped through race, class, gender, sexuality, disability, or religion? How can the potential to transform democracy by overcoming adult-centrism be specifically deepened from an intersectional angle? Academic contributions that use an intersectional perspective to address deliberative democracy for youth are rare. In terms of formal politics, the greatest inequality between children, adolescents and adults is the lack of voting rights. However, a broad intersectional approach needs to highlight the various social structures that operate at an often-subtle level to privilege youth that come close to the white, Eurocentric, cis-gendered, androcentric, heteronormative, abled-bodied norm and exclude, discriminate, marginalize, and silence those who are othered. These racialized, gendered, heteronormative, able-bodied social structures restrict social inclusion and exercising citizenship and lead to increased vulnerability. Thus, revisiting youth and democracy from an intersectional perspective should aim to dismantle structures of exclusion while broadening modes of participation on a structural level.

The few existing contributions highlight, first, that children and adolescents are a heterogeneous group and also a Eurocentric historical construct (Aitken 2018; Khan 2021; Rabello de Castro 2019). Second, they reveal that deliberation and participation must be conceptualized as active processes of empowerment (Laforgue et al. 2022, 66) rather than integration into already-given adult-centered, white, androcentric forms of agenda-setting, communication and decision-making. Here, intersectional approaches to youth as relevant actors of deliberative democracy stress the potential for transforming democracy instead integrating them into existing, limited structures.

Laforge et al. (2022) point out that youth inclusion alone is insufficient for making democracy more democratic: “Incorporating intersectionality into children and adolescents’ participation actions entails acknowledging that inclusion is a necessary condition to ensure social justice, but it is not sufficient in and of itself. Aside from being included or having their voices heard, people need to be guaranteed the conditions necessary for them to exercise their right to participate on an equal footing.” (ibid., 71) Third, the literature stresses that participation is a process of learning (ibid.) and a process that must ensure inclusive interaction (ibid., 70). This also encompasses breaking from adult-centered stereotypes and listening to youth in the first place (ibid., 71). By viewing children as political actors in presence and as political actors who can contribute to democracy precisely through their specific experiences as youth in intersectional power relations rather than “empty” or only future citizens, intersectional youth participation can indeed both transform social inequalities and make democracy more democratic.

However, these contributions on intersectionality, youth and democracy do not systematically elaborate upon how the deliberation and participation of youth from an intersectional perspective might look. Thus, in the remainder of this literature review, we propose using heuristic dimensions as a crucial intersectional lens when thinking about how to intersectionally re-conceptualize youth participation in democracy.

6. An intersectional lens for deliberation and participation of youth

This section takes an intersectional perspective and proposes expanding the conceptualization of deliberative democracy that also approaches youth as political citizens and develops an intersectional lens that can approach the democratic deliberation and participation of youth. The intersectional lens is based on the epistemology that intersectionality is a reflexive tool that invites both researchers as well as political actors to make the complexity of multiple, interwoven relations of power, exclusion and violence visible and to aims to transforming them. Here we follow Crenshaw’s proposal for conceptualizing intersectionality as structural and political intersectionality (Crenshaw 1991, 1251). Therefore, the following intersectional lens does not offer an a priori list of categories of oppression or a best-practice guideline for “how to do intersectionality” in deliberative and participatory processes. Rather, it entails dimensions of reflection that we consider crucial for doing democracy and research on democracy from an intersectional perspective.

Our proposed intersectional lens is based upon the premise that intersectionality itself is a democratizing device because it aims to transform injustice and also expand political agency and the political. In their research on participation of queer youth in the undocumented youth movement in California, Veronica Terriquez, Tizoc Brenes and Abdiel Lopez propose that intersectionality can serve as a “collective action frame” (Terriquez/Brenes/Lopez 2018, 261) that can “bring people together and incites action” (ibid.) in a democratizing way, not least because the politicization of

the every-day experiences of oppression can transform these experiences into a political resource (ibid., 263). Intersectionality as a political frame in political action has a threefold potential (ibid., 260).⁴ First, intersectionality as democratizing logic can serve as a “diagnostic frame” (ibid., 262) where political actors develop a shared understanding of a social phenomenon as problematic or unjust. Importantly, this does not need to be based on shared or similar experiences; rather, it is the shared understanding of a problem that arises from an intersectional lens and can serve as politicizing force. Second, intersectionality can serve as “motivational frame” (ibid.) for people to take collective political actions “by prompting individuals to become empowered around their multiple identities” (ibid., 268). Being aware of how various forms of oppression are entangled, but also being aware of being both oppressed and privileged (Collins 1993) can induce a political will for agency and change. Third, intersectionality can serve as “prognostic frame” (Terriquez/Brenes/Lopez 2018., 263) that collectively helps define a political action or intervention. Intersectionality as a prognostic frame politicizes the multiple forms of oppression, which can help it contribute to coalition building (ibid., 264). Furthermore, it can also “inform the internal practices of organizations so that they operate as inclusive spaces for members who occupy different marginalized identity categories” (ibid., 264). As such, intersectionality can be an epistemic and political tool that allows institutions and organizations to “adopt various strategies to attend to the needs of participants’ multiple identities through diversity trainings, separate spaces for specific identity groups” (ibid., 264). Next, we propose an intersectional lens for deliberative democracy and youth that aims to expand the understanding of democracy.

First, the outlined understanding of intersectionality as an approach that enables the radical questioning of power structures requires deliberative democracy to be a “critical practice, itself always subject to scrutiny for antidemocratic, institutionalized, or newly emerging values, practices, and norms” (Ackerly 2007, 51). From an intersectional perspective, deliberative democracy must be a radical invitation to challenge given racialized, postcolonial, gendered, classed, heteronormative, ability-centered and age-centered structures of power, exclusion and violence. Therefore, deliberation from an intersectional perspective is an epistemological attitude of questioning and unsettling of what seems to be given. An intersectional lens on youth and deliberative democracy stresses the necessity to use intersectionality as a tool of questioning and disrupting hegemonic logics rather than as a tool for maintaining the status quo.

Thus, an intersectional approach to deliberative democracy removes deliberation from its abstract, normative setting and puts the social conditions of democracy at the forefront. An inclusive intersectional deliberative democracy is centered around the necessity to reflect the social conditions of democracy and the white, androcentric, heteronormative, ability-centred and adult-

⁴ Terriquez et al. have conducted research with activists, making their reference to democracy is indirect. However, we consider their three-fold frame practical for linking intersectionality and democracy.

centred norms that have shaped and still shape political institutions, political communication and political subjectivity. Hence, such deliberation is always a *transformative* process that aims to make power structures visible and transform them. In a neoliberal era, and in reference to discourses that assume “post-racism” and “post-feminism”, intersectional deliberative democracy must particularly focus on social structures and not reduce oppression to an aberration or the action of hateful individuals.

An approach that links democracy to the transformation of social structures also implies expanding deliberation and participation to youth because viewing them as citizens expands the realm of political actors and democracy itself. Furthermore, this approach views the multiple, interwoven structures of oppression that shape youth’s every-day life as a starting point for people to enter the political realm. Thus, an intersectional lens on youth participation and deliberation focuses on whether institutions like (youth) parliament, the public sphere, schools, homes and families can address the social frames of democracy. Furthermore, it demonstrates the need for institutional changes in the public, political institutions, and also schools and youth organizations. Here, it serves as a critical tool that asks if modes of participation and deliberation aim to make substantial transformations or if they solely attempt to include and assimilate youth in existing political structures without transforming these structures or social injustice.

Second, an intersectional approach to deliberative democracy is committed to negotiating the accessibility of deliberation and participation and substantially broadening it. An intersectional perspective is premised upon gender, class, race, migration regimes, sexuality, ability and age being gatekeepers that structure formal and informal access to processes of deliberation. Accessibility can be formally and informally restricted: Formally through nationality and citizenship regimes or age regulations; informally through adult-centred, white, cis-gendered, classed, ability-centred norms of political agency and political participation and communication. Social barriers like language barriers, citizenship status, energy, resources, physical accessibility, and perceptions of oneself and the other of belonging all shape access to deliberation and participation (Ackerly 2007, 48; Yuval-Davis 2006, 2007). Here, an intersectional perspective is a crucial reminder that historical modes of exclusion in the racialized, gendered, classed, ability-centred “interlocking systems” (Collins 1993, 29) of exclusion and oppression remain active and shape who counts as political subject and who is viewed as political subject. Empirical research shows that when recruitment processes for deliberative processes occur, the typical attendees are white men of higher socio-economic status (Strolovitch 2006; Urbinati/Warren 2008), which shows that powerful norms still shape the accessibility of deliberation and participation. Although the internet may open the participatory process, it is still restricted along traditional lines of power and exclusion, but with the addition of an algorithmic power relation.

Therefore, an intersectional lens for deliberative democracy and youth supports reflecting on how multiple, interwoven modes of oppression formally and informally shape accessibility. Assuming that children and youth participation arise from fulfilling deliberative democracy's ideal of inclusion, as argued above, deliberative democracy must be designed so that "unique barriers to participation in terms of access and meaningful participation (age-based restrictions; need for parental consent; 'age-blind' mechanisms that are not designed for or adapted to children, etc.)" (Zlontnik Raz/Almog 2023, 92-93). At the same time, it must acknowledge that multiple barriers may exist. Expanding upon Drake's proposal to "Make anti-racism part of deliberative design" (2003, 104), an intersectional approach to the accessibility of deliberative democracy is based upon: "Making intersectionality part of deliberative design" (ibid.). Here, concrete practices for broadening the forms of deliberation include a plurality of languages, creating smaller groups, and developing evaluation forms to avoid or minimize cultural and discursive exclusions. Therefore, an intersectional lens on youth and the accessibility to deliberation and participation reflects formal and informal racialized, classed, gendered, heteronormative, ability-centred and age-centred barriers: Who can afford to take part in youth parliaments? Who has physical access to public deliberation formats? Who is able to participate without being afraid of being mobbed in school politics? Who is considered eligible for political participation? Moreover, an intersectional perspective scrutinizes the causes of formal modes of exclusion of marginalized youth and how this relates to class, religion, gender, nationality, disability or informal exclusion. Furthermore, it also examines informal barriers to participation like norms or expected behaviours that prevent some marginalized youth from considering themselves eligible to participate in democratic practices. Likewise, an intersectional lens focuses on the need for a political solution to overcome these formal and informal barriers and obstacles and asks if exclusion can be politicized on an institutional level.

Third, an intersectional deliberative democracy must go beyond an institutionalist understanding of democracy, which does not offer political agency to marginalized people and marginalized youth. Agenda-setting and policy-making cannot be reduced to politics 'from above;' rather, democracy is constituted at the margins. This approach comes close to Young's; argument that activists play a vital role for democracy (2001) because marginalized political actors have a deeper insight into society: "The deliberative democrat claims that parties to political conflict ought to deliberate with one another and through reasonable agreement try to come to an agreement on policy satisfactory to all. The activist is suspicious of exhortations to deliberate because he believes that in the real world of politics, where structural inequalities influence both procedures and outcomes, democratic processes that appear to conform to the norms of deliberation are usually biased toward more powerful agents. The activist thus recommends that those who care about promoting greater justice should engage primarily in critical oppositional activity, rather than attempt to come to

agreement with those who support or benefit from existing power structures” (ibid., 248). Similarly, Fung uses “deliberative activists” (Fung 2005) to stress the vital importance of the experiences and voices that are perceived as marginal from an institutionalist lens.

Collins (1986) has described Black feminists as “outsiders-within” in white, androcentric institutions that equip them with specific knowledge about the institution and society that subjects who more closely resemble the hegemonic norms lack. Linking Collins argument about outsiders-within to Nishiyama’s argument (2017) about youth participation in democracy shows that intersectional deliberative democracy that also addresses youth lies in the specific potential for marginalized youth to bring issues and problems into deliberative processes that would otherwise remain unpoliticized.

Thus, an intersectional perspective on youth and deliberative democracy can also expand the realms of democratic participation and deliberation. Democracy does not only take place in institutional settings, but also in the informal settings of youth’s every-day life. Because youth are formally excluded from many political processes such as voting, democratic processes with youth are not and cannot solely be found in the formal realm of politics. Hence, this expansion of the localization of democracy is a key contribution from youth to democracy. Thus, deliberative democracy with and by youth can occur in multiple locations including the streets, in youth organizations, and at schools. Thus, youth participation is not restricted to the public sphere and also shows that politics take place in the private sphere. Here, an intersectional lens on deliberative democracy aligns with the feminist expansion of deliberative democracy that shows how deliberative democracy requires a multiplicity of public spheres (Fraser 1997). Therefore, institutions like schools, youth organizations, and families can also be realms of politics and must decide if they allow and enable marginalized youth to participate.

However, an intersectional lens also cautions that these multiple public spheres are not automatically free of power structures. Hence, an intersectional lens must also scrutinize how the internet as a core present-day communication platform can serve as a democratic public sphere for youth or if it reproduces forms of exclusion. Problems like racist, anti-queer, and anti-trans hate campaigns demonstrate that the internet is not a non-hierarchical space for youth participation. This often results in marginalized youth avoiding the internet as a political platform. Thus, an intersectional lens broadens the scope of deliberation by including a plurality of political spaces; but at the same time it keeps in mind that public spaces are not power-free spaces but are deeply structured by power and are therefore not automatically the antipode of institutionalized politics.

Fourth, deliberative democracy from an intersectional perspective must be based on multiple forms of communication. Drawing on the intersectional critique that ‘rationality’ is neither objective, neutral nor a priori definable, but rather a sedimentation of the “white supremacist capitalist patriarchy” (Hooks 1984), deliberative democracy must depart from the illusion of a solely rational,

disembodied deliberation and integrate forms of political communication like embodied and emotional modes of expression. As Black feminists like Audre Lorde (1984c) have argued, emotions are a deeply political form of communication. Lorde conceptualizes anger as a political response to racism: “Anger of exclusion, of unquestioned privilege, of racial distortions, of silence, ill-use, stereotyping, defensiveness, misnaming, betrayal, and co-optation.” (ibid.: 124). It is a political mode of expression that can be “translated into action” (ibid.: 127). Thus, an intersectional deliberative democracy must be a political terrain where emotions are viewed as a political response to exclusion and marginalization and must therefore be heard instead of being silenced under the white, androcentric illusion of ‘unemotional rationality’. Furthermore, an intersectional perspective on deliberative democracy must also go beyond the narrative that deliberation is a disembodied process, as demonstrated by Iris Marion Young’s approach and insistence on bringing in bodies into the realm of democracy. Based on her embodied phenomenology (1980), she argues that political communication must abandon an androcentric, Eurocentric, ability-centred notion of ‘rationality’ and include bodily and affective forms of political communication. In particular, it should acknowledge the history of modern Western democracies and their exclusion of Black people and other people colour, white women, queer and non-binary people, people with disabilities and youth through assumed ‘inferior’ bodies. Likewise, in light of modern Western democracy longstanding illusion of political communication being a disembodied activity, incorporating the body as a political agent is crucial for an intersectional deliberative democracy. This also entails transforming perceptions of a “good” political citizen and a “true” form of political participation. Again, this intersectional expansion of democracy overlaps with the expansion of democracy that views youth as political citizens. As we argued earlier, solely *including* youth into existing structures of deliberative communication is insufficient. Rather, expanding democracy to intersectional youth can also broaden the modes of democracy, and it is this plurality of political communication that will make democracy more democratic.

Given that the exclusion of youth—especially marginalized youth—from democracy is usually legitimated through their emotional and bodily ‘immaturity,’ expanding modes of deliberation and participation is key to an intersectional perspective for broadening the political channels of democracy. An intersectional lens on democracy and youth is a critical reminder that democracy is not only based on (supposed) disembodied, ‘rational’ argumentation, but must include various modes of political communication like storytelling and also uses emotions as political modes of communication. Thus, an intersectional lens on democracy and youth must guarantee that participation and deliberation also allow marginalized youth to integrate both their bodily and affective experiences of exclusion and discrimination as political communication. Furthermore, an intersectional youth democracy must provide multiple modes of communication as equal tools

instead of the rational mode of argumentation as established by classical Habermasian deliberative democracy.

Fifth, from an intersectional perspective, deliberative democracy is tightly related to learning processes. Because it is embedded in social inequalities and social injustices, and deliberation in a structurally unjust society must shift the responsibility for change from marginalized people to those who are privileged, deliberation does not assume that the ‘most rational’ argument will succeed. Rather, deliberation must be reconceptualized as processes that help learning to listen to those who are marginalized. Deliberation is a learning process, which requires those who are privileged to unlearn their privileges by learning to listen to those who are marginalized (Spivak 1988). Hence, as Paulo Freire (2000) argued in the pedagogy of the oppressed, democracy must also facilitate processes of conscientization, i. e., be(coming) critically aware of structures of oppression and actively acting to resist them.

An intersectional perspective on deliberation demonstrates the vital need for deliberation to entail a willingness and political ability to learn from each other and to learn from differences. This resembles Audre Lorde’s Black feminist perspective: “As women, we have been taught either to ignore our differences, or to view them as causes for separation and suspicion rather than as forces for change. Without community there is no liberation, only the most vulnerable and temporary armistice between an individual and her oppression. But community must not mean a shedding of our differences, nor the pathetic pretense that these differences do not exist” (Lorde 1984a, 112). Lorde continues: “Certainly there are very real differences between us of race, age, and sex. But it is not those differences between us that are separating us. It is rather our refusal to recognize those differences, and to examine the distortions which result from our misnaming them and their effects upon human behavior and expectation.” (Lorde 1984b, 115) Deliberation implies to listen and learn from differences instead of subsuming them under universalist goals.

Such a perspective also de-centers the focus of consensus in deliberative democracy. As a “democratic pedagogy of counter-narration” (Gibson 2020, 439; Ackerly 2007, 48), deliberation needs to be pluralized. Consensus is only possible in a society with structural, intersectional inequalities by silencing marginalized experiences and voices. Grasping deliberation as processes that incite the “willingness of those with power to listen, and give sufficient weight to, the critiques of people experiencing oppression” (Drake 2023, 103) also shows why it is necessary to re-think the political as plural instead of singular. Thus, an intersectional perspective reminds us to conceive conflicts as elements of democracy instead of silencing them by aiming for consensus as a democratic goal. An intersectional approach to deliberative democracy can also broaden the understanding of democracy to enable conflicts instead of silencing them.

A crucial element in these democratic learning processes is undoing and rejecting hegemonic narratives (Gibson 2020, 443) and making new radical images of society and the political hearable

(Banerjee 2021, 288; see his argument for decolonial imaginaries). Because an intersectional perspective sees society as structurally unequal, deliberative democracy must open spaces for participants to imagine “the world as it could be” (Gibson 2020, 442). For democratic pedagogy, Gibson states what this implies: “Therefore, a democratic pedagogy of counter-narration would intentionally ask students to investigate, question, and speak out against the taken-for-granted “common sense” of political discourse and power and to instead narrate or amplify perspectives that challenge the political status quo and that make visible how power operates within political discourse and action” (Gibson 2020, 440; see also Freire 2000). As a process of questioning the existing social order, deliberation enables and invites using counternarratives and counter-storytelling as a democratic tool against a normalization of the multiple and intersection modes of exclusion. “Counternarratives can be personal stories, the retelling of other people’s stories, composites of stories, and imaginings of stories not yet realized, and they can be based on experience, research, literature, or hope.” (Gibson 2020, 440)

This willingness to learn from each other is key to deliberation and has a crucial consequence for understanding the political: The definition of “political” or a “political problem” does not precede modes of deliberation. Rather, learning and un-learning from each other through deliberation can also transform what is considered political in the first place. Therefore, as Ackerly argues when drawing on John Dewey, deliberation is a process that “changes the deliberants’ preferences and understandings of the political” (Ackerly 2007, 50), not least by being affected through the others. Hence, deliberation is a “transformative experience” (Ackerly 2007, 56).

An intersectional perspective on youth and deliberative democracy fundamentally changes the political setting: Opening democracy to marginalized youth does not aim to integrate them into existing adult-centred modes of deliberation and participation. Rather, it decenters privileged adults and re-conceptualizes democratic politics as processes where marginalized youth can be equal political actors who should be listened to by those in privileged positions within an adult-centered, androcentric, white democracy. Politics as a transformative experience also implies reversing the roles of those who deliberate and those who listen and learn. Therefore, marginalized youth are crucial political actors whose (formal and informal) exclusion will leave democracy incomplete.

Sixth, because an intersectional approach strengthens democracy, intersectional democracy must also challenge the existing modes of implementing and operationalising categories of difference and hierarchical relations. Since marginalized youth remain excluded from democracy, deliberate democracy cannot exclude a reflection upon categories that marginalize and exclude young people. Rather, the political negotiation of categories should be considered an element of democracy. However, as stated above, determining which category people belong to and how they distinguish themselves requires acknowledging the fluidity of categories and not applying an

essentialist approach to them. This also means recognising that intersectionality is flexible sometimes also antagonistic, with Patricia Hill Collins (2000) arguing that categories can also interact in a way that simultaneously creates privileges and disadvantages— which the democratic negotiation of intersectionality must also account for. Thus, democracy requires deliberating about categories in order to politicize structures of oppression and use categories as form of political mobilization that can politicize experiences of marginalization and exclusion. However, an intersectional lens on youth and democracy must avoid essentialising and de-contextualizing categories. As stated above, ignoring the intersectionality and heterogeneity of youth risks further marginalizing young people who are already marginalized, especially if deliberation and participation are mis-understood as being based on essentialised categories. An intersectional lens can help examine how young people make sense of and push back against the boundaries of ostensibly neutral and static social identity categories. As Azmitia and Mansfield (2021) have argued, the following set of questions are relevant for an intersectional lens on democracy and youth: “(1) Who is included in a social identity category? And are there diversity levels of within-group variability in a social identity, such as gender, race, class, or sexuality? When does the dissimilarity between group members render the identity category incoherent?

(2) What roles do inequality and oppression play in the construction of identity intersectionality?” (ibid) Furthermore, deliberative democracy that focuses on the participation of marginalized youth must also ask how “multiple minoritized identities serve as a source of pride and power for youth, particularly those engaged in social activism” (ibid.). Therefore, a core question for a deliberative democracy and marginalized youth is if “there similarities in the intersectional experiences of youth who vary in their social identities? For example, is there a common ground for youth who experience different identity configurations and oppressions?” (ibid.).

Integrate the negotiation of categories into the realm of democracy itself also implies politicizing the matter of what categories count as norms of political agency. For example, if a mini public of youth only consists of white participants, race or whiteness might not be considered relevant. Hence, an intersectional lens on democracy requires critically investigating which categories have the privilege to sometimes remain absent. Likewise, an intersectional approach to democracy must reflect upon how privileged categories like whiteness or heteronormativity allow political subjects to automatically “sink” into the white and heteronormative political institutions like “sinking into a comfortable chair” (Ahmed 2004, 148). Thus, given that intersectionality can also serve as a reminder for privileged people to reflect upon how their structural privileges make them to fit into political institutions.

Seventh, an intersectional perspective on deliberative democracy and youth also needs to acknowledge the boundaries of deliberation. As long as multiple and interwoven power structures shape society, deliberation will have its limits. Deliberative democracy of and by youth can shift

boundaries; however, they cannot entirely transform them, which would require transforming social structures. However, an intersectional perspective on democracy is a vital reminder to keep the limits of deliberation in mind. Thus, questions such as “Who can be heard in the process of deliberation?” and “Who is absent?” must also be part of deliberation.

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